

What do Germs and Criminals Have in Common?

Testing a Biological Explanation for the Age Crime Curve

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The age crime curve provides the probability distribution of crime by age. Population level age crime curves generally indicate that criminal activity is low in early childhood, rises rapidly to a peak in late adolescence, and then declines with age until few people commit crimes in old age. There have been few successful attempts to fit a mathematical model to the age crime curve. Quetelet (1831/1984) had proposed that changes in strength, passion, and reason over the life course provided a biological explanation for the age crime curve. This paper provides a test of Quetelet's hypotheses that is limited to an examination of how changes in strength and brain capacity match changes in arrest rates over the life course. The results of these analyses suggest that the age crime curve can be considered to be a cumulative probability distribution with three sections, 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98. A mathematical model that assumes that criminal propensity is normally distributed and posits that Z-scores for the age crime curve are a combination of the strength and brain capacity trajectories over the life course appears to provide an excellent fit to the age crime curve data. The implications of these findings will be discussed.

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The thesis of this paper is that it is not necessary to understand “crime” in order to understand the reasons for the “age crime curve.” This may seem to be a highly counterintuitive statement, but the evidence presented in this paper suggests that the well known age crime curve (Farrington, 1986) is a statistical artifact that is due almost entirely to the development of strength and mental capacity over the life course. Differences in criminal propensity, which is the likelihood that a person will commit a crime, appear to control the level of crime at the individual and group levels, while biological developmental factors appear to control the age distribution of crime. If this model is correct, it would appear to have important consequences for the study of crime over the life-course.

The age crime curve was documented by Quetelet (1831), who found that crime rates rise rapidly in adolescence and decline almost as rapidly in adulthood. He suggested that the age distribution of crime was caused by normal human growth and development over the life course. It seems illogical that biological developmental processes such as changes in strength or mental capacity would, in and of themselves, cause crime. If biological development caused crime, everyone should be a criminal. However, there seems to be strong evidence that changes in strength and mental capacity do cause the age crime curve. If biological development causes the age crime curve, then the causes of criminal behavior must be separate from the causes of the age crime curve. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) also argued that the causes of crime are different from the causes of the age distribution of crime, but never provided a testable theory to explain why this would be the case. A case will be made that Quetelet (1831) was correct, the age crime curve is the result of normal biological development and has little to do with the causes of crime.

The importance of developing an explanation for the age crime curve may not be immediately apparent to some readers. There are two important considerations that need to be addressed, the first is theoretical, and the second is methodological. No theory or method has been found that explains why crime varies as it does with age. It appears that a biological explanation involving the trajectories of strength and mental capacity over the life course, combined with the right statistical model, can provide a parsimonious explanation for the age crime curve.

From a theoretical standpoint, the age crime curve is a population phenomenon that appears to have little to do with individual trajectories of criminal behavior (Blumstein et al. 1986) or other criminological factors (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). However, regardless of the fact that it theoretically should not exist, there is little doubt that there is a general pattern of criminal offending over the life course that needs to be explained. As Macleod, Grove, and Farrington (2012) noted, without an understanding of the “large scale framework” for criminal behavior it is not possible to understand the small scale detail (p. 48). Osgood (2005) suggested that explaining the age crime curve is “one of the most interesting and important challenges of research on crime and the life course” (p. 209). Criminologists agree that there is no generally accepted explanation for the age crime curve (Loeber, 2012; Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Farrington, 2003; Osgood, 2005; 2012; Piquero, Farrington, & Blumstein, 2003; 2007; Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013; Telesca Erosheva, Kreager, & Matsueda, 2012). While the age distribution of crime might not be an issue on many criminologist’s radar, there appears to be a consensus among a small minority of criminologists that a theoretical explanation for the age crime curve is needed.

In contrast to many criminological studies that focus efforts on finding the “differences” between criminals and the rest of humanity, the approach used in the current analyses will be to try to find the “similarities” between criminals and the rest of humanity. It will be suggested that normal human development over the life-course creates constraints on 1) the capacity to commit crimes, and 2) the capacity to avoid committing crimes, and these two factors intersect with 3) individual differences in the propensity to commit crimes, with the result being a population level age crime curve. The two part biological model that will be presented posits that lack of strength seems to act as a limiting factor for the commission of crimes and greater mental capacity seems to act as a protective factor. Acting together over the life course, the developmental trajectories of strength and mental capacity appear to intersect with the distribution of criminal propensity in the population, which causes the distinctive shape of the age crime curve.

The second issue that needs to be addressed regarding the age crime curve is methodological. Although various attempts have been made (Britt, 1992; 1994; Greenberg, 1994; Macleod, Grove, & Farrington, 2012; Sweeten et al., 2013), there does not appear to be a generally accepted mathematical model for the age crime curve. The lack of a mathematical model is causing problems for researchers studying crime rates that vary by age.

In many criminological studies, age is inserted into regression analyses as a linear variable (cf. Agnew, & White, 1992; Brown and Males, 2011). An examination of the age crime curve will reveal that the relationship between age and crime is non-linear. While a linear model may be adequate for some age ranges (cf. Agnew, & White, 1992), it is inadequate for studies that include the transition between adolescence and adulthood. For instance, Brown and Males (2011) did an analysis of income, age, and crime, treating age as a linear variable ranging from

15-69, and found that income level by age seemed to be a stronger predictor of crime than age alone. Shulman, Steinberg, and Piquero (2013) replicated the Brown and Males (2011) study, treating age as a cubic function, and found that income by age had little effect when compared with the effect of age alone. The non-linear effect of age on crime has not been adequately addressed in the criminological literature, and there is a need to determine the “mathematical form” (Britt, 1992) of the age crime curve.

The essence of the approach used in the current article is to take the life course trajectories for strength and mental capacity, convert them to probabilities, subtract a fraction of the mental capacity at each age from a fraction of the strength capacity at each age, and use a mathematical transformation to create the probability distribution for crime at each age. The mathematical models used to test the biological theory presented in this article provides a new twist on an old procedure. The base model used in this article has typically been used in germ warfare in a process called “probit analysis” (Finney, 1947). An examination of the data on strength, mental capacity, criminal propensity, and crime will show that it is possible to create a highly accurate statistical model that explains the age crime curve by using a modified version of the “method of probits” (Bliss, 1934; 1935). This is a statistical method developed to determine the percentage of germs killed by changing levels of antiseptic solutions. Particular attention will be paid to the theoretical basis for the non-linear probit model that was proposed by Brooks (1918). Although the proposed method of modeling the age crime curve was developed to study the dose/response properties of germs in the presence of antiseptics, the methods and theoretical basis developed for probit analysis also appear to provide an excellent model of the age distribution of criminal behavior over the life course. This raises the question, “what do germs and criminals have in common?”

The proposal that the age crime curve is caused by biological factors is not a new idea. The age crime curve was documented by Quetelet (1831), who found that crime rates rise almost exponentially to a peak in late adolescence, and then drop off almost as quickly in adulthood. Quetelet (1831) suggested that developmental changes over the life course in three biological factors, strength, passion, and reason, combine to create the age crime curve. It does not appear that his biological theory has been empirically tested because 1) there has not been sufficient data, and 2) no mathematical model existed to explain the relationship between biology and criminal behavior. The theory proposed in this paper appears to be one of the first to provide any type of empirical test of Quetelet's (1831) model.

The current analyses provide a somewhat simplified test of Quetelet's (1831) theory. Measures of his concept of "passion" will not be included. The proposed test will only include measures of strength and reason. The concept of "reason" will be replaced with the concept of "mental capacity." The term "mental capacity" will remain undefined at this point, as it may represent a combination of several types of mental capacity. In general, the term "brain capacity" could also have been used. While there may be some strong candidates for the exact type of mental capacity that is most important, the exact details remain unclear.

The approach used in the current article has some distinct advantages over previous attempts to explain the age crime curve. This approach provides, 1) a testable theory that is parsimonious, 2) an explanation for the effects of biological development on crime over the life course, and 3) a statistical model that explains why the age crime curve has the unique shape that it does. The resulting two part biological model appears to explain most of the variation in crime over the life course. Regardless of whether the theoretical explanation is satisfactory, the model itself is so accurate, that the result needs some type of explanation.

Some Background

Quetelet (1831) developed a biological theory for the age distribution of crime, claiming that crime peaks in adolescence and declines with age because of changes in strength, passion, and reason over the life course (See Quetelet, 1833/1984; p54-55 for an English translation of his theory). This biological explanation appears to have been generally ignored by most criminologists.

Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) made a number of controversial statements in a review of the age distribution of crime, arguing that 1) the age distribution of crime is invariant across social conditions, gender, and race, 2) is inexplicable with demographic variables related to crime, and 3) does not interact with other criminological variables. They conclude that 4) there is no need for longitudinal research designed to study crime over the life course because 5) the causes of crime are separate from the causes of the age crime curve and therefore, 6) it is not necessary to understand the age distribution of crime in order to understand the reasons for crime. The thesis of the current paper is a corollary of the proposal made by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983). If it isn't necessary to understand the age distribution of crime to understand the reasons for crime, the reverse of this proposition should also be true, it is not necessary to understand crime in order to understand the reasons for the age crime curve.

They did not seem to be opposed to biological explanations for the age crime curve, since they attribute the decline in criminal activity with age to "Maturational reform" or some other equivalent unexplained process (p. 564). While this explanation implies some biological process, they did not try to propose a more explicit biological explanation. See Hirschi and Gottfredson (1986) for a discussion of biology and the age distribution of crime.

Before going into the criticisms of Hirschi and Gottfredson's (1983) core proposals, it should be noted that their propositions do not appear to have been falsified (cf. Sweeten et al., 2013). Most criminologists appear to agree with their position and have adopted the working theory that the reasons for crime and the reasons for the age crime curve are not related. An examination of a typical criminological study will reveal that age is usually included as a control variable and an explanation of the effects of age is not needed to explain the criminological findings. See Uggen (2000) for an exception. For example, Agnew and White (1992) found that a control variable for age had a positive linear relationship with delinquency for subjects 18 and under. Burton, Cullen, Evans, and Dunaway (1994) found that a control variable for age had a negative linear relationship with crime for subjects 18 and over. Burton et al. (1994) did not comment on the fact that age is a risk factor for adolescents (Agnew, & White, 1992), and a protective factor for adults, because this is an unremarkable finding and is considered to be completely separate from the study of the criminological concept of strain. It is assumed that strain is a criminological risk factor for both adolescents and adults, irrespective of the effects of age. A thorough reading of the criminological literature will demonstrate that most criminologists have generally supported the thesis that crime and the age crime curve have separate explanations.

Not all criminologists accept the thesis that crime and the age crime curve are separate phenomena. A number of attempts have been made to refute the various proposals presented by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983). Various criminologists have argued the age distribution of crime is not invariant, or inexplicable, and age is related to other criminological variables, which means that there is a need to study crime over the life course.

Probably the most vocal criticisms of Hirschi and Gottfredson's (1983) proposals have come from criminal career researchers. Vold, Bernard, and Snipes (2002) report that statements about the age distribution of crime made by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) resulted in a "great debate" among criminologists (Pp. 284-291). Vold et al. (2002) suggested that the great debate boiled down to two positions, a "criminal propensity" position, and a "criminal career" position. See Osgood (2005) for another review of the great debate.

In the great debate, Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983; 1985a, 1985b, 1990; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1986; 1987; 1988; 1990) argued that between individual differences in crime rates are caused by stable individual differences in criminal propensity (Vold et al., 2002). The term criminal propensity can mean a number of things, so it will be defined as "the likelihood of committing a crime." The general argument of Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983, Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990) is that rank order differences in criminal propensity are stable over the life course and therefore, age has the same effect on offenders and non-offenders. In essence, they argue that everyone has an age crime curve, but some age crime curves are higher than others. They argued that age apparently has an effect that is separate from criminal propensity, and so age can be ignored in criminological research and the focus can be placed on studying how differences in criminal propensity are related to levels of crime.

The criminal career position was taken by Blumstein, Cohen, and Farrington and others (Blumstein, Cohen, Farrington, 1988a; 1988b; Blumstein, & Cohen, 1987; Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visher, 1986; Piquero et al., 2003; 2007). Criminal career advocates argued that there is considerable variation in individual criminal careers. The focus of criminal career research is generally on determining why some people do not appear to commit crimes, others commit few, and others commit many crimes over the life course. Criminal career researchers suggest that a

typology should be created that consists of innocents, persisters, and desisters (Blumstein, Farrington, & Moitra, 1985). In order to study these various groups, it is necessary to study factors such as participation, starting age, rate of offending, career length, age of desistance, and crime seriousness over the life course (Blumstein, et al., 1986). Criminal career researchers argue that the causes of crime and desistance may be different at different ages and the rank order of a person's criminal propensity can change over time. This means that there is a need for longitudinal research to determine the effects of life circumstances on crime.

One of the more popular typological theories in keeping with the criminal career model was created by Moffitt (1993). She proposed that there are two types of offenders. One type of offender is a very common "adolescence limited" offender that commits crimes in adolescence due to a "maturity gap" between biological development and social maturity. The other type of offender is a "life course persistent" offender that commits crimes over the entire lifespan because of neuropsychological deficits. Moffitt's (1993) theory has resulted in over a hundred studies that attempt to find groups of offending trajectories in the population (Jennings, & Reingle, 2012; Piquero, 2008). Trajectory studies indicate that it is possible to find from 2-7 group trajectories in the population, and that 4 group trajectories is the most common (Jennings, & Reingle, 2012). It does not seem that this line of research has been productive in producing an explanation for the population level age crime curve, although it appears highly likely that there are individual differences in offending patterns and some groups appear to map onto Moffitt's (1993) dual taxonomy (Moffitt, 2006).

While Moffitt (2006) finds support for a dual taxonomy of offenders, there is a concern with the research on group level trajectory modeling that is commonly used to support her model. The modeling approach that is commonly used to find group trajectories may be flawed.

It appears that group trajectories occur in randomly generated data with no groups specified (Skardhamar, 2009; 2010). This suggests that a taxonomy may not be needed to explain the age crime curve, and that a continuous model may produce group trajectories as well.

Another source of opposition to Hirschi and Gottfredson's (1983) proposals has come from criminologists who disagree with the inexplicability hypotheses, which is that the relationship between age and crime cannot be explained by other criminological variables. Efforts have been made to explain the age crime curve with sociological, psychological, and/or temporary biological changes that occur over the life course.

Evidence suggests that overall crime levels vary by gender, race, genetic makeup, personality type, nation, neighborhood, etc. (Ellis, Beaver, & Wright, 2009). Since these variables represent differences in sociological, psychological, and biological factors, it can be difficult to sort out specific causes of the age crime curve.

These debates have created a literal mountain of research on the relationships between crime and various factors. It would seem that there is no simple solution to the problems associated with determining how all of these various factors fit together. The proposal presented here provides one attempt to fit the data together in a coherent framework that can be used to focus efforts to understand how sociological, psychological, and biological factors combine to create "age crime curves" for various groups of individuals with various characteristics.

A More General Theory of the Age Crime Curve

In order to develop a more general theory of the age crime curve that encompasses the sociological, psychological, and biological factors that cause the age crime curve, it will be necessary to develop a set of consistent theoretical propositions. The propositions are as follows, 1) the development of strength and mental capacity across the life course must affect the rate of crime at each age, with a positive relationship between strength and crime, and a negative relationship between mental capacity and crime, 2) the changes in strength and mental capacity are generally independent of factors related to sociological, psychological, and age dependent biological changes over the life course, 3) criminal propensity is a trait that is normally distributed with any large group of humans, with the mean level varying due to sociological, psychological, and biological factors, 4) the relationship between criminal propensity and crime is relatively stable,

Biology and Crime

The first proposition is that ontological changes in strength and mental capacity must have an effect on crime rates over the life course. The possibility that the age crime curve is caused by biological factors is not a new idea. This possibility was suggested by Quetelet (1831), who argued that changes in strength, passion, and reason must affect the age distribution of crime, since strength is low during childhood and old age, when crime is at its lowest, passion is at its highest in adolescence, when crime is at its peak, and crime decreases in adulthood when the level of reason is growing. The following theory is a somewhat simplified version of Quetelet's (1831) proposition. A two part biological model is proposed that posits that life course changes in strength and mental capacity cause the age crime curve.

Recognizing that sociologists, psychologists, and even biologists will find this a difficult proposition to accept, the following argument will be offered to suggest that at some level, this proposition must be correct. This argument is borrowed from the bible (Genesis 18:20-33, New International Version). Abraham tried to talk God out of destroying Sodom and asked if God would still destroy Sodom if fifty good people could be found. When God relented and offered a reprieve if fifty good people could be found, Abraham continued to suggest scenarios with 40, 30, and 20 people until he got God to agree to spare Sodom from destruction if only 10 good people could be found. A variation of this argument is presented to the critics of an ontological theory of the age crime curve.

Regarding strength, would it be feasible for newborn babies to commit a crime? Obviously not. How about one year olds? Difficult. Two year olds? Perhaps they could get a gun and pull the trigger. Still difficult. Take this progression forward. Ask the question, what is the mathematical relationship between strength and the capacity to commit crimes? There must be one. What is it? When is someone fully capable of committing any type of crime? Some crimes, such as assault would presumably require more than average strength and not be feasible until the strength was at its peak. Is the ability to commit any possible crime a sudden transition or is it a gradual one? The following proposal suggests a gradual transition.

Regarding mental capacity. Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) have made a cogent argument that crimes are generally very dumb ideas. Crimes usually result in little gain and can have substantial negative consequences for the perpetrator. One would expect that mental capacity should be related to crime and it is. It is less well known that mental capacity changes over the life course. Does a newborn have the capacity to avoid committing a crime? Probably not, although this proposition would be difficult to test, as newborns do not have the strength to

commit a crime. How about one year olds? How much control do they have? Two year olds? They are pretty violent with each other, but we do not charge them with a crime for biting a playmate.

Moving forward year by year, when does mental capacity reach a point where it is enough to keep the person from doing something that is generally not a good idea? Is there a sudden shift when the entire population has a large enough mental capacity to understand that they should not commit a crime, or is there a gradual transition? What is the mathematical form of the relationship between the growth in mental capacity and crime? The following proposal is that there is a gradual change in mental capacity over the life course and that mental capacity is inversely related to criminal activity.

Ontological Change is Independent of Sociological, Psychological, and Biological Factors

The second proposal is that changes in strength and mental capacity operate independently of sociological, psychological, and biological changes that occur over the life course. This does not preclude the possibility that some type of magnifying effect does not occur. This proposal is that any differences in behavior caused by these factors are independent of changes in strength and mental capacity.

Sociology and Crime

There seems little doubt that there is some type of relationship between sociological factors and crime. The mean group rates of crime vary by nation, state, city, neighborhood, etc. While it is possible that some genetic or psychological factors have an influence on these between group differences, there are undoubtedly sociological forces at work that change the rate of crime between groups.

At the individual level, how do sociological factors, such as a change in identity, shape the level of crime over the life course? Are the changes in sociological factors over the life course independent of ontological processes such as the development of strength and brain capacity? How much difference in the crime rate at various ages would one expect from living in different countries? Is the age of adulthood that much different between countries? What factors would cause sociological variation in the trajectory of crime? Employment practices? Difference in school programs? How much variation should be expected? This is not clear. Although there are substantial between group differences in crime rates, it is not clear how much sociological variation is independent of changes in strength and mental capacity. If a standard relationship could be developed between strength, mental capacity, and crime, sociologists could start looking at between group variation in the within group trajectories. For the present, it will be proposed that there is no variation in crime over the life course that is due to sociological factors.

Psychology and Crime

There seems to be little question that there are between individual differences in levels of criminal propensity. Various psychological factors such as low self-control, personality traits, neurological deficits, psychopathy, etc. all are related to differences between individuals in crime rates. Again, as with sociological factors, the question related to the age crime curve is, how much variation is there in the trajectories of crime over the life course, and does this variation show up at the population level? Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) suggest that there are differences in the height of the criminal trajectories, but that the shape is relatively stable. Criminal career researchers would suggest that there is variation in the shapes of the trajectories. How much of this individual variation in developmental trajectories remains after biological

changes in the mean strength and mental capacities are accounted for? This is a good question. For the moment, it will be proposed that there is no variation in the age crime curve due to psychological processes. Changes in strength and brain capacity will account for all of the variation over the life course.

Other Biological Factors

Some biologists would argue that changes in other biological factors such as levels of gonadotropins lead to a change in the life course trajectory. The only way to prove these theories would be to compare group trajectories. For the purposes of this article, the null hypothesis will be adopted. It will be suggested that other biological factors do not cause a change in the age crime curve that is independent of changes in strength and mental capacity.

A Testable Hypothesis

From the previous discussions, it is suggested that only changes in strength and brain capacity have an effect on the age crime curve. There is probably individual variation due to these factors, but at the population level, any changes will disappear, leaving only the influences of strength and brain capacity. Sociological, psychological, and other biological factors will have no influence on the age crime curve. This provides a testable proposition: Hypothesis 1) The age crime curve for any group of individuals will explain the age crime curve for any other group of individuals. For instance, the age crime curve for males will explain the age crime curve for females, and the age crime curve for whites will explain the age crime curve for blacks.

A Trait Model of Criminal Propensity

In the model that follows, it will be suggested that criminal propensity is a trait. This is consistent with Gottfredson and Hirschi's (1990) position that criminal propensity is caused by a trait called low self-control. Traits are usually normally distributed in the population (Allport,

1961). Several theorists have suggested that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population (Rowe, Osgood, & Nicewander, 1990), therefore the first proposal is that criminal propensity is a trait that normally distributed in any large group of humans, with some people having high levels and others having low levels.

A model of the relative distributions of criminal propensity for males and females is shown in Figure 1a. In this model, the two population groups, males and females, have different mean levels of criminal propensity. The criminal propensities for both groups are normally distributed, and the two distributions combined create a larger normal distribution for the entire population. The standard deviations for the normal distributions in the model are equal, but need not be.

If males and females have their own normal distributions, it can also be assumed that each age group has its own normal distribution as well. This model is shown in Figure 1b. Note that the distributions for the age groups are shown as larger than they actually are. The data from the age crime curve tells us that one year old children have a lower mean level of criminal propensity than 10 year old children. Ten year old children have a lower mean level of criminal propensity than 18 year old adults. Each age group has a separate normal distribution of criminal propensity with a different mean. The standard deviations could be different, but for now, it will be assumed that they are the same. All of the single age distributions add up to a combined normal distribution for criminal propensity at all ages.

Figure 1: Criminal Propensity Distributions by Gender and Age

1a) Criminal Propensity by Gender

1b) Criminal Propensity by Age

Source: U.S. Crime Rates (NIBRS, 2012), U.S. Population Data (Census, 2012)

This model is compatible with both of the criminal propensity positions taken by Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) and criminal career researchers. Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) would argue that individual within group criminal propensity is stable; a person with high criminal propensity at age 10 has high criminal propensity at age 18. Criminal career proponents would argue that individual within group criminal propensity is unstable; the position within the group criminal propensity distribution can vary with age. A person with low criminal propensity at age 10 could have high criminal propensity at age 18, and vice versa. Taking either a stable or unstable position will not affect the discussion that follows.

The Mathematical Relationship between Criminal Propensity and Crime is Stable

It is proposed that there is a stable mathematical relationship between criminal propensity and crime. In any society, behaviors that deviate sufficiently from the norm will be charged as a crime. It is further proposed that the level of behavior that is considered criminal will tend to

change very slowly. This will create a crime cutoff where behaviors over a certain level of deviance will be charged, and those below that level will be ignored.

The question is, what will be the mathematical relationship between criminal propensity and crime? The theoretical basis for an answer is derived from theories of germ warfare. In both Figure 1a and 1b, a crime cutoff line is shown. It will be assumed that all persons with a criminal propensity higher than the crime cutoff line will commit crimes and all persons lower will be assumed to be law abiding. This prediction follows from theoretical properties of normal distributions that have been explored extensively in antiseptic studies of germ kill rates (Bliss, 1935; Brooks, 1918; Finney, 1947).

Brooks (1918) noted that when antiseptic agents were applied to germ cultures with linearly increasing dosages, the germ kill rate could be described as a sigmoid response curve. Brooks (1918) suggested that the reason for this phenomenon was that, at any given level of antiseptic, the germs with a resistance to the antiseptic above that level would live, and the germs with a resistance to the antiseptic below that level would die. The number of germs killed would therefore be all of the germs whose resistance fell below the cut off line. This theoretical approach became the basis for probit analysis (Bliss, 1935; Finney, 1947). Bliss (1935) demonstrated that the explanation proposed by Brooks (1918) appeared to be due to the properties of the cumulative distribution for a normal curve.

In the case of the age crime curve, rather than repeated applications of an antiseptic, the level of criminal propensity is changing by age. A preliminary examination of what is expected to occur will be proposed using age as a linear variable. Presume that the model in Figure 2b is correct. At age one, the normal curve for the criminal propensity of one year old children is far to the left in the total distribution. The number of crimes committed would be the area under the

normal curve that fell to the right of the crime cut off line. The formula for the probability of any point on the normal curve is a squared exponential,

Where

μ is the mean of the normal distribution

x is the distance from the mean

σ is the standard deviation of the normal distribution

A simplification of this formula is created by setting the mean of the distribution to zero by subtracting the mean from each value and setting the standard deviation to one by dividing each value by the standard deviation. If the mean is zero, the term $(x - \mu)$ then becomes equal to x , which is replaced with the letter "z" and the standard deviation disappears from the formula. The letter z is referred to as a z-score and represents the distance from the mean of the distribution. That convention will be followed here. The formula for the standard normal distribution is

In order to calculate the probability for all events one side of x , a cumulative probability is calculated. In a continuous distribution, an integral is used to calculate the cumulative probability. This formula adds all the probabilities from z to infinity.

If it is assumed that x is the crime cutoff line and that it does not move appreciably from year to year, then the population mean (μ) will change each year with age, resulting in a different value for z each year. The population crime rate can then be calculated as the cumulative

probability for that z-score. The question becomes, how does z change with time? If the answer to this question can be determined, it will be possible to infer the causes of the age crime curve.

The Changes in Criminal Propensity with Age are caused by Changes in Strength and Mental Capacity

The benefits of a z-score model become apparent when an attempt is made to compare strength, mental capacity, and crime rates. These are three essentially different things. The problem is comparable to trying to find a relationship between oranges, apples, and bananas. A way to develop a mathematical relationship must be found. Once the relationship is developed, the values for strength and mental capacity must be determined and fit to the model. This two part process is used below.

A Mathematical Formula for Combining Non-similar Quantities

The solution to combining values from different types of measures lies in a property of normal distributions and z-scores found by people doing test development. Test developers have found that sets of test scores can be converted to standard normal distributions and combined. Generally, this is an additive process. Two or more z-scores are each multiplied by a constant, and added together to give a combined z-score. The constant makes it possible to add two values from distributions with varying means, standard deviations, and relative effects on the outcome of interest.

In this case, the different types of values are mean strength, mean mental capacity, and mean crime rate by age. The formula for this relationship is as follows,

$$Z_{(\text{Crime, Age})} = b * Z_{(\text{Strength, Age})} - c * Z_{(\text{Mental Capacity, Age})}$$

In this formula, the z-score for strength is considered to be positive, which reflects the proposition that strength has a positive relationship with crime, and the z-score for mental capacity is considered to be negative, which reflects the proposition that mental capacity has a negative relationship with crime. As the total z-score grows, the probability of crime increases. The formula for the probability of a crime at any age is then the formula for the standard normal curve with the z-score for crime determined by the values of the z-scores for the levels of strength and mental capacity over the life course. A constant “d” is added to the formula to reflect the fact that the standard deviation of the criminal propensity distribution is not known, but is presumed to be constant.

The formula for “d” is a constant that should have the following value,

While the formula shown above appears formidable, probabilities for standard normal distributions can be easily calculated in Excel with the NormSDist() function, and Z-scores can be calculated from probabilities with the NormSInv() function. This will permit some relatively easy tests to be performed.

The Trajectories of Strength and Mental Capacity over the Life Course

The challenge is to determine the measures of strength and mental capacity to use. There are many types of strength and many types of mental capacity. Which types of strength and mental capacity are related to crime? What are the trajectories that will be used? In order to answer these questions, it is necessary to study the trajectories of strength, mental capacity, and crime over the life course.

One of the most consistent findings is that there are curvilinear trajectories for strength and mental capacity. Both rise almost linearly through childhood and adolescence, remain relatively stable over much of adulthood, and then decline almost linearly in old age. The addition of two linear equations provides a third linear equation. In this case, the formula for z is as follows,

$$z(\text{Crime, Age}) = (a + b*(\text{Age})) - (c + d*(\text{Age}))$$

Where a and b are intercepts and b and d are slopes for the linear trajectories.

This simplifies to

$$z(\text{Crime, Age}) = (a - c) + (b-d)*(\text{Age})$$

While it may not be possible to solve for a,b,c, and d, it is possible to assume that z(Crime, age) is a linear function when the trajectories of strength and mental capacity are linear, as in childhood and adolescence and old age.

The formula using Excel is as follows,

$$z(\text{Crime, Age}) = \text{NormInv}(P(\text{Crime, Age}))$$

Therefore, combining the previous two formulas gives,

$$\text{NormInv}(P(\text{Crime, Age})) = (a - c) + (b-d)*(\text{Age}) = j + k*(\text{Age})$$

Where $a-c = j$ and $b-d = k$

This provides the second testable proposition; Hypothesis 2) the z-score for that age crime curve is a linear function with a positive slope during childhood and adolescence, and a linear function with a negative slope during later stages in the life course.

The standard normal distribution has a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. The probability for a can then be calculated by

Where z is the number of standard deviations from the mean

If the standard deviation is not known, the formula for the probability expressed in terms of z and σ is,

The formula for the area under the curve is the sum of the area under the normal curve between the value and infinity. The formula for the area can be expressed as an integral of the form,

Fortunately, there is a simplified method of calculating this value in Microsoft Excel using the NormInv() function.

The Dynamics of Criminal Propensity

For the time being, it will be assumed that there is a certain level of propensity, called a crime cutoff, where those with a propensity above a certain level are guaranteed to commit a crime, and those with a level below a certain point will not commit a crime. This is not accurate, but will permit an easier explanation. A more complex model can be developed later.

Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983)

The criminal career model, has not been successful in producing a generally accepted solution to the age crime curve (Loeber, 2012; Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Farrington, 2003; Osgood, 2005; 2012; Piquero, Farrington, & Blumstein, 2003; 2007; Sweeten, et al., 2013; Telesca Erosheva, Kreager, & Matsueda, 2012). The relationship between individual factors and the age crime curve is not clear. A recent attempt to determine a relationship between 40 of the best known variables related to crime and the age distribution of crime was able to explain 69% of the variation in crime from ages 15-25 that would have been explained by age alone (Sweeten et al., 2013). The authors conclude that more data is needed if a better model fit is to be obtained. They suggest that a simple solution is probably not possible.

Future progress using the methods proposed by Sweeten et al. (2013) is highly doubtful. In order to provide more explained variance, variables unrelated to the 40 already used would be needed. Since these variables represent some of the best known covariates of criminal behavior, it is unlikely that new variables will emerge. Other problems with the study include the use of a criminal sample, which is unrepresentative of the entire population, and using an age range (15-25) which does not represent the entire life course. In order to explain crime at the other sections of the life-course, even more variable would probably be required. The result would be a piecemeal approach and little likelihood of developing a general theory to explain the age crime curve.

If further progress is to be made in explaining the age crime curve, new approaches are needed. The criminal career approach is a valid method of producing evidence, but it is essentially a bottom up approach. Data accumulated at the individual level is accumulated and used to generate inductive propositions that can be used to build theory. The process used by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) and Quetelet (1831) is a top down approach. Theories are generated and then tested to see if they fit reality.

While data on individual careers is useful, it is difficult to take that information and determine why the average person tends to commit more crimes at age 18 than any other age. The age crime curve is a population phenomenon. It represents the average crime rate for the average person. Individual reasons for crime are many and varied (Ellis, Beaver, & Wright, 2009) and individual variables related to crime may not have enough statistical power to remain in the equation for the population rate of crime by age.

In addition to the two main positions of “criminal propensity” and “criminal careers” suggested by Vold et al. (2002), a small but important third position was also taken for studying the age crime curve. Some criminologists tried to find the “mathematical form” of the age crime curve (Britt, 1992). Rowe, Osgood, and Nicewander (1990) made an important contribution by proposing a latent trait model of criminal propensity. They suggested that criminal propensity can be thought of as a latent trait, which is an unobservable, but measurable, quantity. They hypothesized that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population and that the level of criminal activity rises exponentially as criminal propensity rises. While this finding, by itself, did not explain the age distribution of crime, it provided an important theory of the distribution of crime across individuals.

Britt (1992) tested gamma and log-normal distributions with the age distributions for a number of crime types and found that both mathematical models had high explained variances when explaining the shapes of various crime distributions. Greenburg (1994) suggested that a modified chi-square distribution provided a better fit than the gamma distribution for the individual crime age crime curve data. An important point raised by Greenburg (1994) was that many different mathematical fits might be found, but these are problematic if there is no theoretical basis for their use. In the discussions that follow, the theoretical base will be developed before the mathematical model.

A Biological Explanation for the Age Crime Curve

Before examining the connection between germs and criminals, some background information is needed. First, it is important to justify the need to explain the age crime curve. This may prove difficult. Most criminologists appear to get by without explaining why crime rates vary with age. Second, some background on existing theories and research is needed. Is a new approach really necessary? Third, it is important to lay the groundwork for this explanation. Although it appears that an understanding of crime is not needed in order to understand the age crime curve, the explanation should explain why there is a connection.

The first issue is in regards to the importance of the age crime curve problem. Is it really necessary to understand the age crime curve? It does not seem to be in many instances.

The statements about the age distribution of crime made by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1994) were highly controversial and resulted in a “great debate” among criminologists (Vold,

Bernard, & Snipes, 2002; pp. 284-291). Vold et al. (2002) suggest that the great debate boiled down into two competing positions, a “criminal propensity” position, and a “criminal career” position. Both positions propose different theories to explain the age crime curve.

The criminal propensity position is that there are differences between people in their likelihood of committing a crime. This position was taken by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983; 1985a, 1985b, 1990; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1986; 1987; 1988; 1990). They argued that differences in criminal propensity occur because people vary in their levels of self control (Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990), and that the relative rank order of a person’s self control is stable over the life course, irrespective of age. Age is simply a “brute fact” that does not require explanation (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). In general, research on self control indicates a relationship with crime (Pratt, & Cullen, 2000), but most studies tend to follow the control variable approach and this has not lead to progress in explaining the age crime curve. Longitudinal studies on the stability of self-control have generally supported the stability thesis, suggesting that self-control is similar in stability to other personality traits (Arneklev, Cochran, & Gainey, 1998; Burt, Harbin, Simons, & Simons, 2006; Grasmick, Hay, & Forrest, 2006; Mitchell, & MacKenzie, 2006; Tittle, Bursik, & Arneklev; 1993; Turner, & Piquero, 2002; Winfree, Taylor, He, & Ebensen, 2006).

The criminal career position was taken by Blumstein, Cohen, and Farrington (1988a; 1988b; Blumstein, & Cohen, 1987). Criminal career advocates argued that there is considerable variation in individual criminal careers and it is necessary to study participation, starting age, rate of offending, career length, age of desistance, and crime seriousness over the life course. Criminal career researchers would argue that the rank order of a person's criminal propensity can change over time.

The criminal propensity position is that some people have a "trait" that makes them "crime prone" (Caspi et al., 1994). Various traits associated with increased criminal behavior include low self control (Gottfredson, Hirschi, 1990),

The net result of this debate is a consolidation by criminologists into three positions that vary from largest to smallest. The largest group of criminologists appears to agree with the position of Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983), The age crime curve is invariant, inexplicable, and non-interactive, and there is no need to address issues related to age in criminological theories. This group takes a "control variable" approach, treating age as important, but inexplicable. A smaller group of criminologists appears to feel that it is important to study the individual in order to determine how crime changes over the life course. This group uses a "bottom up" approach. An even smaller and much less popular position involves trying to find a solution to the age crime curve using population data. This third group uses a "top down" approach. The results of each of these three approaches will be explored.

Ignoring the age crime curve by treating it as an inexplicable control variable is almost guaranteed to result in no progress toward finding a solution. Other criminologists are interested in finding a solution to the age crime curve, and take a “bottom up” approach by studying individual offenders. This approach, which is typical of the criminal career model, has not been successful in producing a solution to the age crime curve (Loeber, 2012; Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Osgood, 2005; 2012; Piquero, Farrington, & Blumstein, 2003; 2007; Sweeten, et al., 2013; Telesca Erosheva, Kreager, & Matsueda, 2012). Researchers have found many facts related to individual criminal careers, but there are still many unanswered questions about why some individuals participate in criminal activities more than others (Farrington, 2003). How do all of the individual factors related to crime combine to create the age crime curve?

The relationship between individual factors and the age crime curve is not clear. A recent attempt to determine a relationship between 40 of the best known variables related to crime and the age distribution of crime was able to explain 69% of the variation in crime from ages 15-25 that would have been explained by age alone (Sweeten et al., 2013). The authors conclude that more data is needed if a better model fit is to be obtained. They suggest that a simple solution is probably not possible. Future progress using the methods proposed by Sweeten et al. (2013) is highly doubtful. In order to provide more explained variance, variables unrelated to the 40 already used would be needed. Since these variables represent some of the best known covariates of criminal behavior, it is unlikely that new variables will emerge. Other problems with the study include the use of a criminal sample, which is unrepresentative of the entire population, and using an age range (15-25) which does not represent the entire life course. In order to explain crime at the other sections of the life-course, even more variable would probably

be required. The result would be a piecemeal approach and little likelihood of developing a general theory to explain the age crime curve.

There have been a few other attempts to develop a theory to explain the age crime curve. Sampson and Laub (1993) discuss turning points and transitions caused by employment, marriage, and joining the military, but it does not appear that enough people do this at the same exact time as would be required to cause the rapid switch in crime in late adolescence.

Moffitt (1993) developed a dual taxonomy to explain the fact that many people commit crimes in adolescence, and few people commit crimes in adulthood. Jennings and Reingle (2012) report that 105 studies have been done to determine the group trajectories of violence, aggression, and delinquency and that the most frequent number of groups found is four, followed by three. This is more than the two groups proposed by Moffett (1993), and there does not seem to be a theory to explain there would be more than two groups.

In a distant third place, behind the mainstream “control variable” approach, and the “bottom up” approach, there is a small group of criminologists taking a “top down” approach to the study of the age crime curve. The results of their analyses suggest that there is a need to combine the “criminal propensity” position and the “

, and a “criminal career”

Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) used the proposed disconnect between crime and the age crime curve in order to support several conclusions. In addition to the invariance, inexplicability, and invariance hypotheses, they suggested that longitudinal research is not needed to understand crime. These four hypotheses set off Baldwin (1985) and Greenberg (1985) argued that the age crime curve can be explained. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983; 1985a) disagreed. Gottfredson, & Hirschi (1986) went on to criticize the criminal career paradigm

The great debate consisted of a series of articles written by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983; 1985a, 1985b, 1990; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1986; 1987; 1988) in response to articles written by criminologists interested in the study of criminal careers at the individual level (Blumstein, Cohen, & Farrington, 1988a; 1988b; Farrington, 1986), and criminologists interested in providing other explanations for the age crime curve.

that you should understand germs.

Criminologists have been aware for some time that crime rates plotted by the age of offender follow a distinctive “age crime curve” (Farrington, 1986). Quetelet (1831) plotted the age distribution of crime and found that the age crime distribution is highly skewed with crime rates rising rapidly in adolescence and declining almost as rapidly in adulthood. There is an ongoing debate in the criminological literature about the best approach to studying the age crime curve. This debate was particularly heated in the 1980s (Baldwin, 1985; Blumstein, Cohen, & Farrington, 1988a; 1988b; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1986; 1988; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983; 1985a; 1985b; 1990; Farrington, 1986; Greenberg, 1985). Currently, discussions and research are ongoing, with little consensus between criminologists about the reasons that crime has such a strong nonlinear relationship with age (Loeber, 2012; Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Osgood,

2005; 2012; Piquero, Farrington, & Blumstein, 2003; 2007; Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013; Telesca Erosheva, Kreager, & Matsueda, 2012).

Statements made in an article by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) started the debate over the age crime curve. The essence of their argument was that the age crime curve is invariant across social conditions, inexplicable with currently available criminological variables, and not related to other criminological variables, and the best course of action would be to just ignore it. Ignoring the age crime curve would appear to be the approach taken by most criminologists. Age is generally included as a control variable in statistical models (along with sex and race) with very little discussion about why age is directly related to delinquency in adolescence (cf. Agnew and White, 1992), and inversely related to crime in adulthood (cf. Burton, Cullen, Evans, & Dunaway, 1994).

The most vocal opposition to Hirschi and Gottfredson's (1983) suggestions to ignore the age crime curve has come from developmental and life-course criminologists, who promote the study of individual criminal careers by examining the trajectories of crime covariates over the life-course (Blumstein et al., 1988a; 1988b; Farrington, 1986; Laub, & Sampson, 2003; Loeber, 2012; Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Moffitt, 1993; Osgood, 2005; 2012; Piquero et al., 2003; 2007; Sampson, & Laub, 1993; Sweeten et al., 2013). Criminal career researchers have taken the position that the age crime curve can be explained if enough data is accumulated that is related to how individual criminal trajectories unfold over the life course. In a recent attempt, Sweeten et al. (2013) were able to explain 65% of the variance in criminal behavior that was related to age.

Another source of opposition to Hirschi and Gottfredson's (1983) invariance thesis has come from research that indicates that age crime curves are not completely invariant. There is variation in the peak age of offending over time for different crime types (Steffensmeier, Allan,

Harer, & Streifel, 1989), and for different groups of offenders (Jennings, & Reingle, 2012; Piquero, 2008). Britt (1992)

It would appear that Hirschi and Gottfredson's (1983) advice to ignore the age crime curve has some fundamental flaws. This approach does not provide a theoretical explanation for why crime rates change with age, and simply including age as a control variable in statistical analyses runs the risk of model misspecification if the relationship between age and crime is not a simple linear relationship as is often presumed (cf. Agnew, & White, 1992; Burton et al, 1994). While the age crime rate might be invariant across many social conditions, and unexplainable with demographic variables, attempts to explain the age crime curve should continue.

The approach taken by criminal career researchers also appears to be flawed. They have discounted the possibility that a simple explanation for the age crime curve exists (Sweeten et al., 2013), and therefore, criminologists are missing an opportunity to develop a parsimonious explanation for the age crime curve. The multiple factor approach taken by Sweeten et al. (2013) violates the principle of Ockham's razor (Boehner, 1957), which states that the simplest solution that fits the facts should be found. Theories that attempt to explain the age crime curve should use as few variables as it possible.

The key to explaining the age crime curve would appear to be related to finding an explanation for the invariance in the age crime curve noted by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983). If the shape of the age crime curve is similar for people of different sexes, races, countries, and time periods, it would seem logical, as they suggested, that sociological variables are not the cause. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) avoid stating an obvious solution to the problem, which is that the age crime curve is due to biological factors. They did not address the issue of biology until later (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1985a; 1986; 1995).

This article represents an attempt to fill a rather large hole in the study of criminal behavior. There is a general lack of understanding of why crime rates change with age. Criminologists have known for some time that when crime rates are plotted by the age of offenders, they follow an “age crime curve” (Farrington, 1986). The age crime curve was documented by Quetelet (1831/1984), and is found in population statistics collected from both men and women, in various time periods, and with various cultures (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). When crime rates are plotted by age, the crime rates for the very young and the very old tend to be almost zero. Crime rates climb almost exponentially from childhood to about age 18, and then drop almost as rapidly as people become adults. Although there has been considerable speculation about why crime varies with age, there is no generally accepted explanation for the age crime curve (Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Osgood, 2005; Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013).

The primary thesis of this paper is that a radically different approach is needed if criminologists are going to be able to explain why crime rates change the way they do with age. In this article, a statistical method called probit analysis (Bliss, 1935; Finney, 1947) will be used in conjunction with data on the life course trajectories of physical strength and mental development to develop a plausible biological explanation for the age crime curve. Probit analysis was developed to help specify the ability of germs to resist the effects of antiseptics. It

appears that germs and criminals share a common feature in that both the germ's propensity to resist antiseptics and a criminal's propensity to commit crimes are normally distributed in their respective populations. Changes in the crime rate with age appear to be caused by the intersection of the developmental trajectories of strength and mental capacity with the normally distributed level of criminal propensity in the population.

In the statistical model proposed, strength increases the capacity for crime and mental capacity decreases the likelihood for crime. Using U.S. age crime curve data from 1996-2006 (NIBRS, 2012), the explained variance in the age crime curve for this statistical model is about 95%. The accuracy of this model suggests that there is highly credible evidence that the age crime curve is primarily a biological phenomenon, intersecting at almost right angles with sociological and psychological factors.

This finding supports the contention by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990) that the age crime curve operates independently of psychological and sociological factors.

It should be noted in advance that the qualifier "plausible" must be used to describe this explanation because it would be extremely difficult to use actual data on the life course trajectories of strength and mental capacity to test this explanation at the present time. Complete datasets do not exist and this model is highly sensitive to the shapes of the life course trajectories of strength and mental capacity as well as factors related to the mean and standard deviation of the normal distribution for criminal propensity.

However, if this model is correct, there may be important implications for developmental science as well as criminology. These results suggest that it may be just as advantageous to use the age crime curve to help developmental scientists determine how strength and mental capacity

change over the life course as it would be to test how changes in strength and mental capacity generate the age crime curve.

The key propositions of this model are as follows. 1) Criminal propensity, which is the likelihood that a person will commit a crime, is normally distributed in the population. 2) The mean and standard deviation of the normal distribution for criminal propensity vary due to biological, psychological, and sociological factors. 3) Individual levels of criminal propensity are highly dynamic and vary in time frames that range from seconds to the entire life course. 4) The life course trajectories of two biological factors, strength and mental capacity, interact to create the age crime curve. 5) Physical strength is directly related to criminal propensity, it follows a curvilinear path over the life course and peaks at about age 25. 6) Mental capacity is inversely related to criminal propensity, it also follows a curvilinear path over the life course, and it peaks at about age 30. And, 7) the shape of the age crime curve results from the intersection between normal distribution of criminal propensity with the age distributions of physical strength and mental capacity over the life course.

The explanation provided in this article is a departure from most of the previous research and commentary on the age crime curve. Before proceeding with a review, it will be helpful to consider the two plots of the U.S. age crime curves for males and females. This data represents all crimes reported to the police in the U.S. in the eleven years from 1996 to 2006 (NIBRS, 2012) combined with the U.S. population by age during those same years (Census, 2012). The total crimes per year of age were divided by the number of people at each age expressed in 100,000 persons. This provides an accurate crime rate for each year of age.

Figure 1: Total Arrests per 100,000 Persons by Age and Gender for United States from 1996-2006

Source: U.S. Crime Rates (NIBRS, 2012), U.S. Population Data (Census, 2012)

From an examination of Figure 1a, it seems clear that the peak offending rate for males is about four times as the peak offending rate for females. The age crime curves for males and females in Figure 1a appear to be quite different in shape. However, if the data for the males and females is expressed as the percent of the total crimes for males and females at each age as in Figure 1b, it appears that the age crime curves are almost identical. Both curves come to a sharp peak at about the same time.

There have been several basic approaches taken in attempts to explain the age crime curve. The most popular approaches to explaining the age crime curve will be characterized as the “ignore it” approach, the “close approximation” approach, and the “divide and conquer” approach. The approach used in this article will be more rigorous than these three approaches. These three approaches have not been successful, and it is suggested that a mathematical model based on germ science produces a plausible biological explanation for the age crime curve that is theoretically sound and empirically defensible.

The “ignore it” approach

Gottfredson and Hirschi (1983) have become the champions of the “ignore it” approach. They argued that the age crime curve is something that is both ubiquitous and inexplicable, and therefore, there is no need for criminologists to explain it. They demonstrated that the age crime curve is invariant for males and females, across time periods, and in various cultures, and this suggests that it cannot be explained by sociological variables (see Gove, 1985). They note that many variables related to criminal behavior have similar relationships with crime, regardless of the age of the individual. These data suggest that criminologists can simply add control variables when they conduct their statistical analyses to remove any variation related to age, and the studies will produce valid results.

The “ignore it” approach to the age crime curve is very popular with criminologist. For example, consider two strain studies. In the first study, the subjects are adolescents, and delinquency rates go up with age (Agnew and White, 1992). In the second study, the subjects are adults, and crime rates go down with age (Burton, Cullen, Evans, & Dunaway, 1994). The authors of the second study did not need to explain this apparent discrepancy, presumably because the change in direction is expected. Criminologists expect crime rates to go up for adolescents, and down for adults, and so they can ignore the results.

Although it may be difficult to determine why variation in age is correlated with crime in opposite directions for adolescents and adults, the “ignore it” approach would seem to be inadvisable. There appear to be two fundamental flaws to the “ignore it” approach related to theoretical and statistical problems. First, this approach does not lead to a theory of why age is related to crime and so much of the variation in crime rates remains unexplained. Second, in most statistical analyses used in criminology (cf. Agnew, & White, 1992; Burton et al., 1994),

age is inserted into regression models as a linear variable. A visual inspection of the age crime curves shown in Figure 1 indicates that the relationship between age and crime is not even approximately linear over certain age ranges. This means that, depending on the range of ages included in the studies, statistical models using age as a control variable are probably not specified correctly when a linear relationship between age and crime is assumed.

The “close approximation” approach

Most of the theories and methods used to explain the age crime curve have tended to be approximate and non-mathematical in nature. Theorists find biological, psychological, or sociological variables that appear to rise in adolescence and fall in adulthood and suggest that they play a role in causing the age crime curve. This type of theorizing provides interesting speculation, but it is generally not going to provide a testable solution to the age crime curve.

Various factors that have been suggested as possible candidates for causing the age crime curve are a peak in “thrill and adventure seeking” (Baldwin, 1985; see Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1985 for a reply); a peak in testosterone levels (Gove, 1985; Ellis and Walsh, 2000; Walsh, 2009); a change in identity with the transition to adulthood (Giordano, Cernkovich, & Rudolph, 2002; Laub, & Sampson, 2001; 2003; Maruna, 2001; Shover, 1996); the desire to find a mate and produce children (Kanazawa, 2003; Kanazawa, & Still, 2000); getting married, getting a job, or joining the military (Sampson, & Laub, 1993); maturation (Glueck, & Glueck, 1937); social maturation (Moffitt, 1993); changes in strength, passion and reason (Quetelet, 1831/1984); moral development, cognitive development and/or changes in physical capacity (Adams, 1997), and immaturity of judgment (Cauffman, & Steinberg, 2000). There is very seldom a test done to determine the exact nature of these factors to crime, and so they remain speculative.

The “divide and conquer” approach

There have been a number of attempts to explain the age crime curve using a “bottom up” approach. This approach involves trying to determine how individual trajectories combine to create the age crime curve. This approach has been the focus of criminal career research.

Criminal career researchers have taken the approach that the age crime curve is important, but it must be explained at the individual and group level and not the population level. The focus in criminal career research is to look at individuals over time and determine whether certain factors are correlated with certain types of criminal trajectories.

There are certain fundamental flaws with the criminal career approach. The biggest flaw is that it is generally non-theoretical in nature. There is very little effort to explain why the age crime curve exists. The age crime curve is one of the most important findings in criminology. Something causes crime to rise in adolescence fall in adulthood. It would seem very important to understand why this occurs as it places limits on efforts to change individual trajectories.

A two factor biological explanation

The typical response to the age crime curve such as ignoring it, coming up with close approximations, and dividing the problem into sub-parts have not proven to be very successful. In this article, an attempt will be made to develop and test a mathematical model to explain why crime rates vary with age. This model assumes that changes in strength and mental capacity over the life course cause crime to vary over the life course. While the parameters in this model may vary, it is suggested that this model will fit males and females, as well as people from various countries and historical eras, which suggests that the age crime curve is largely independent of other biological, psychological, and sociological factors.

In order to explain the age crime curve, there is a need to examine how “criminal propensity” varies both between and within individuals and groups. Criminal propensity is defined as the likelihood that someone will commit a crime, and it varies markedly between individuals and groups and also within individuals and groups of individuals with the passage of time. Various theories have been developed to explain differences in criminal propensity between and within individuals and groups (Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990; Moffitt, 1993; Sampson, & Laub, 1993). For the purposes of the analyses that follow, the primary point is that these differences exist.

The two factor biological explanation begins with the premise that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population. There is not very much research to support this hypothesis, but the need for this premise will become apparent. The hypothesis that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population was proposed by Wilkins (1965). It was suggested that sinners are on one end of the distribution of deviance and saints on the other. An analysis of data from the National Youth Survey done by Clarke and Weisburd (1990) suggests that deviance is more likely to be normally distributed when minor forms of deviance are included in the analysis. Wikström (2009) reports that criminal propensity was normally distributed in a random sample of adults assessed in the Peterborough Community Survey. These studies provides some support for the proposition that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population.

A corollary to the proposition that criminal propensity is normally distributed is that criminal propensity in any sub-populations with sufficient variation will also be normally distributed. For instance, in Figure 2a, hypothetical distributions of criminal propensity are displayed for males and females. Males have a higher mean level of criminal propensity. The

sum of these two sub-populations is also a normal distribution with a mean value midway between the other two. The standard deviation for the total population is slightly larger than for the sub populations.

An extension of the sub-population corollary is that criminal propensity at each age should also be normally distributed. This model is shown in Figure 2b. The mean level of criminal propensity at age 10 is less than the mean level of criminal propensity at age 18, just as females have a lower criminal propensity than males. However, these populations are both normally distributed. Note that the actual size of the populations for age 10 and 18 in relationship to the total distributions would be much less than shown in Figure 2b. The important concept is that the mean level of criminal propensity increases with age until about age 18 and then declines until death. It would be possible to plot a normal distribution for every year of age, and the total sum of these distributions would also be a normal distribution.

It is further hypothesized that crimes are only committed when a threshold of criminal propensity is reached. These thresholds are indicated in Figures 2a and 2b by the vertical lines marked as "Crime Cut Off." It is proposed that any persons whose criminal propensity is higher than the crime cut off will commit a crime, and any persons with a lower level of criminal propensity will avoid committing crimes.

If the model in Figure 2a is accurate, then it is expected that as people age, the level of criminal activity will follow a sigmoid curve. This prediction follows from properties of normal distributions that have been explored extensively in antiseptic studies of germ kill rates (Bliss, 1935; Brooks, 1918; Finney, 1947). Brooks (1918) noted that when antiseptic agents were applied to germ cultures with linearly increasing dosages, the germ kill rate could be

described as a sigmoid response curve. Brooks (1918) suggested that the reason for this phenomenon was that, at any given level of antiseptic, the germs with a resistance to the antiseptic above that level would live, and the germs with a resistance to the antiseptic below that level would die. The number of germs killed would therefore be all of the germs whose resistance fell below the cut off. This theoretical approach became the basis for probit analysis (Bliss, 1935; Finney, 1947). Bliss (1935) demonstrated that the explanation proposed by Brooks (1918) appeared to be due to the properties of the cumulative distribution for a normal curve.

A preliminary explanation using age as a linear variable will be provided. Presume that the model in Figure 2b is correct. At age one, the normal curve for the criminal propensity of one year old children is far to the left in the total distribution. The number of crimes committed would be the area under the normal curve that fell to the left of the crime cut off line. The formula for the normal curve is a squared exponential,

Where

μ is the mean of the normal distribution

x is the distance from the mean

σ is the standard deviation of the normal distribution

The standard normal distribution has a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. The probability can then be calculated by

Where z is the number of standard deviations from the mean

If the standard deviation is not known, the formula for the probability expressed in terms of z and σ is,

The formula for the area under the curve is the sum of the area under the normal curve between the value and infinity. The formula for the area can be expressed as an integral of the form,

Fortunately, there is a simplified method of calculating this value in Microsoft Excel using the NormInv() function.

Between individual and between group differences in criminal propensity have been fairly easy to document and measure with cross sectional analyses. Wolfgang and Figlio (1972) demonstrated that some individuals are much more likely to commit crimes than others. Group differences in criminal propensity also exist. It is well known that crime rates vary markedly between males and females (Quetelet, 1831/1984), and crime rates vary markedly between countries (United Nations, 2013). The reasons for this variation are more difficult to determine. There are possible biological, psychological, and sociological differences between individuals, males and females, as well as between the groups of individuals who reside in different

countries, and this multi-level variation creates a problem when trying to determine why there is a difference between individuals and groups in their levels of criminal propensity.

Within individual differences in criminal propensity are harder to document due to the need for repeat assessments, varying time frames needed for measurement, and problems identifying periods when criminal propensity is waning. Repeated measurements of criminal propensity are needed to determine whether changes in propensity have occurred. Criminal propensity varies within individuals in moments, days, weeks, months, and years, and over the life course. Biological, psychological, and sociological factors change over various time frames, which means that measurement must also be done at multiple time intervals. Determining the cause of within individual differences in criminal propensity is also hampered because it is difficult to determine when the offender's risk has decreased (Maruna, 2001). Data indicates that there is intermittency in offending and this is not well understood.

The solution to the problem of determining the cause of differences in criminal propensity is to identify similarities and differences between and within individuals and groups. Statistical analyses are typically done using cross sectional and longitudinal research designs in order to determine whether individuals and groups are the same or different, when holding other variables constant. The most common model for statistical analyses is the linear model, and this model is adequate for many cross sectional phenomena. It is becoming increasingly apparent that the linear model is inadequate for determining the characteristic dynamics of longitudinal biological processes, and scientists are beginning to explore nonlinear statistical models to study longitudinal data.

The age crime curve is a population based statistic that measures the cross sectional rates of crime over the entire life course. A cursory glance the age crime curves for males and females

shown in Figure 1 reveals that the age crime curve for both males and females follows a non-linear trajectory. The curves in Figure 1 were generated by calculating the average numbers of crimes reported at each year of age for all people in the United States for the eleven years from 1996-2006 (NIBRS, 2012). It is clear that there is a sizable difference in the height of the age crime curves for males and females. The shapes of the curves could be similar, but at this scaling, it is hard to tell. The challenge for criminologists is to try to explain any similarities and differences between the two curves, when holding other variables constant.

A Review of the Literature on the Age Crime Curve

Criminologists have been taking an increasing interest in the “dynamics” of criminal behavior. Dynamics are patterns of behavior. Studies have shown that there are substantial differences between and within offenders in the dynamics of criminal behavior.

Usually, there is little theoretical discussion about why these variables tend to have a significant relationship with crime rates. It is not clear why criminologists spend so little time discussing these variables, but one reason could be that age, gender, and race represent biological differences between individuals. There seems to be a general reluctance to discuss the effect of biology on crime rates. When age, gender, and race are discussed, the focus is generally on sociological and psychological reasons that these factors cause differences in crime rates. It seems that the reluctance to focus on biology is a major oversight for criminologists and that biological differences need to receive more attention in discussions of crime. In particular, the developmental trajectories of biological factors such as physical strength and mental capacity should be examined to determine the biological effects on crime over the life course.

In this article, an attempt will be made to provide a relatively simple and empirically supported biological explanation for a phenomenon that has perplexed criminologists for the past 180 years. This phenomenon is the age distribution of crime, which has come to be known as the age crime curve (Farrington, 1986). The age crime curve was documented by Quetelet (1831/1984), who demonstrated that crime rates are almost nonexistent for children under ten; begin to rise rapidly in childhood and adolescence; come to a sharp peak in late adolescence and early adulthood; drop almost as rapidly in adulthood as they rose in childhood; and end with few crimes committed by people who reach old age. After 180 years of searching, there does not appear to be a generally accepted explanation for the age crime curve (Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Osgood, 2005; Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013).

Quetelet (1831/1984) had proposed a biological explanation for the age crime curve, arguing that it was caused by life course changes in three biological factors, strength, passion, and reason. The problem then, as it has been until now, is that there did not seem to be a

satisfactory mathematical solution that could explain the relationship between these biological factors and the age crime curve. In the discussions that follow, passion will be ignored, and the term “reason” will be referred to as “mental capacity.” It is proposed that a highly accurate mathematical model for the age crime curve can be developed with only two biological factors, strength and mental capacity.

The proposed mathematical solution to the age crime curve phenomenon requires the use of scientific methods developed to determine the capacity of germs to resist the effects of antiseptics. The reader may wonder what germs and criminals have in common. The answer seems to be that a germ’s propensity for resisting the effects of antiseptics, and a person’s propensity to commit crimes are both normally distributed in their respective populations. Because of this common feature of having normally distributed propensities, there appears to be a statistical similarity between germs and criminals. From this statistical similarity, it is possible to develop a mathematical solution that explains how changes in physical and mental capacities over the life course combine with the normal distribution of criminal propensity in the human population to create the age crime curve.

It appears that the difficulty criminologists have had in determining the relationship between strength, mental capacity, and the age crime curve occurred because the connection between these factors requires a nonlinear transformation of strength and mental capacity trajectories using a method called probit analysis (Bliss, 1935; Finney, 1947). The transformation of factors related to normal distributions using probit analysis was developed to help researchers determine the relationship between germ kill rates and antiseptics. It is suggested that the theories developed for “germ science” will enable criminologists to develop a

mathematical explanation for the relationship between the two biological factors, strength and mental capacity, and the age crime curve.

In the proposed solution, probit analysis will be used show how the life course trajectories of strength and mental capacity cause the age crime curve. The process involves using the Z-scores and probabilities for a normal curve. If data on the developmental trajectories of human physical and mental capacity over the life course is combined and transformed from Z-scores into probabilities, the result is the age crime curve.

A Brief Overview

A reviewer for an early draft of this article suggested that it was important to provide some justification for a study of the age crime curve. The importance of understanding the effects of biological development on crime would seem to be obvious, but apparently, it is not. Criminologists generally tend to ignore the effects of age on crime. For example, Agnew and White (1992) tried to determine the effects of strain on delinquency rates for adolescents and included age as a control variable. Age had a consistent significant positive relationship with delinquency. Two years later, Burton, Cullen, Evans, and Dunaway (1994) tested the effects of strain and self-control on adult crime and found that age had a generally significant negative relationship with crime. Although the authors did comment on the age/crime relationship, there was no attempt made to explain the positive correlation between age and crime, or the fact that age is positively associated with crime when adolescents are studied (Agnew, & White, 1992), and negatively associated with crime when adults are studied (Burton et al., 1994). Age/crime data are generally treated as not important to the discussion of criminological theories of crime. This would appear to be a serious oversight. Age appears to be one of the most consistently

significant variables in studies of crime, and it would seem to be important to discover the cause of this relationship if criminologists are going to be able to explain criminal behavior.

Criminologists did not always avoid biological explanations for the age crime curve. Quetelet (1831/1984) argued that the biological maturation process almost guaranteed the existence of the age crime curve. He reasoned that crimes are seldom committed by the very young and very old, when strength is at its lowest, and crime peaks in young adulthood when strength is at its peak. This suggests that changes in strength over the life course must have an effect on crime rates. Similarly, he argued that passion also peaks in late adolescence, and passion causes of some types of crime. Finally, reason grows as people age and crime rates should be expected to decline with age as people become better able to weigh the consequences of their actions.

In more recent times, criminologists have largely avoided the mention of the “B” word (Biology). Matza (1964) discussed the reasons for criminologist’s concerns with biology. These concerns date back to the theories of Lombroso (1876/2006) and his conceptualization of the “criminal man.” This type of theoretical approach suggests that criminal behavior is pre-determined and that notions of free will do not apply. The result has been a general avoidance of biological theories of crime.

Greenberg (1977) acknowledged that some variation in crime could be expected due to biological processes, but that biological processes could not provide the sole solution. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) analyzed the age distribution of crime and found that it is similar over various time periods and social conditions. They suggested that sociological explanations would not be able to provide an answer to why crime varied with age. While their statements implied that the age crime curve might be caused by biological factors, they avoided any explicit

statement that the age crime curve was caused by physical maturation processes. They suggested the age/crime relationship was one of the “brute facts of criminology” (p. 552) and that criminologists should simply accept the fact that crime declines with age and that attempts to explain this fact could be abandoned.

Gove (1985) went on to discuss the age distribution of crime and also argued that sociological explanations were inadequate. He analyzed labeling theory, conflict theory, functional theory, social control or containment theory, differential association, and anomie theory. These theories all predicted that crime should increase in adulthood and not decline, and so they could not explain the fact that crime rates rise in adolescence and decline in adulthood.

The proposition by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) and Gove (1985) that sociological factors are not able to explain the age crime curve appeared to have the opposite effect of the one intended. Rather than refraining from trying to find a sociological solution to the age crime curve, criminologists began a concerted effort to determine why and how criminal behavior changed over the life course. Efforts to develop sociological solutions to the age crime curve increased.

Sampson and Laub (Sampson, & Laub, 1993; Laub, & Sampson, 2003) proposed that age graded informal social control was the cause of the reduction in crime rates in adulthood. As people became adults and got a job, joined the military, or got married, they took on more adult roles and the level of crime declined.

Sampson and Laub (2001) argued that there was an identity transformation that occurred as people became adults. As people became adults, they gave up the delinquent ways of adolescents and began to consider themselves to be adults, who did not commit crimes.

Moffitt (1993) proposed a biosocial explanation for the age crime curve. She suggested that crime rates rise in adolescence because of a maturity gap that results because adolescents reach biological maturity before they reach social maturity. Biological maturity occurred in adolescence and was caused by the physical changes that occurred during puberty. Crime rates declined for a large group of individuals called “adolescent limited” offenders because of social maturation. Those with crime rates that do not decline in adulthood were called “life-course persistent” offenders. The proposed reason for the lack of decline in criminal activity with age was neuropsychological deficits. Moffitt’s (1993) use of the term “social maturation” was apparently more palatable to criminologists than the term “biological maturation.”

A non-theoretical approach to studying criminal behavior over the life-course was taken by criminal career researchers (Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visher, 1986; Blumstein, Farrington, & Moitra, 1985; Piquero, Farrington, & Blumstein, 2003; 2007). Criminal career researchers study the characteristics of criminal behavior such as participation, rate of offending, seriousness of crimes committed, and career length (Blumstein et al., 1986). Criminal career research was motivated by a study done by Wolfgang, Figlio, and Sellin (1972) that indicated that some offenders commit far more offenses than others (Piquero et al., 2007). The results of the Wolfgang et al. (1972) study suggested that criminal propensity differs substantially between individuals, and therefore, if the criminals with the highest propensity for crime can be selectively incapacitated by long prison terms, the overall crime rate will drop (Blumstein et al., 1986). The age crime curve creates a problem for the selective incapacitation theory. If individual crime rates diminish with age, even though there may be between individual difference in criminal propensity, then selective incapacitation would not be as effective because

even the worst criminals would have lower levels of crime with age (Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1988; 1990).

Despite any apparent similarities or dissimilarities between germs and criminals, determining the relationship between strength, mental capacity, and criminal propensity would appear to be a highly important effort for the field of criminology. The age crime curve is one of the most well established facts about criminal activity over the life course (Hirschi, Gottfredson, 1983), but there is still a debate about what causes it (Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013). Without a good explanation for the age crime curve, it is difficult to determine what might cause deviation from the average trajectory of criminal activity (Telesca, Erosheva, Kreager, & Matsueda, 2012).

(Sweeten et al. 2013).

Quetelet (1831/1984) was one of the first people to document that the level of crime begins at a very low level in childhood, rises to a sharp peak in late adolescence, and then declines almost as rapidly for adults as they age, resulting in very low levels of crime for people over 60. This distinctive pattern in the level of crime over the life course has become known as the age crime curve (Farrington, 1986).

There seems to be little doubt that the age crime curve exists, but there is still a debate about what causes it (Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013). The explanation of the age crime curve is of critical importance for the field of criminology. Osgood (2005) suggested that the

explanation of the age crime curve is “one of the most interesting and important challenges of research on crime and the life course” (p. 209).

Quetelet (1831/1984) was one of the first people to suggest that the age crime curve was due to biological changes in strength and brain capacity over the life course. He argued that levels of crime changed over the life course due to changes in strength, passion, and reason. Strength and passion increases during childhood, during a period when reason is not fully developed, leading to an increase in crime during that period. Then, as the ability to reason increases with age, and levels of strength and passion decrease, the level of crime declines as people grow older. Quetelet (1831/1984) stated, “In considering only these three elements, strength, passion, and reason in man, it could be said almost a priori what must be the degrees of the propensity for crime at different ages” (p. 54). In essence, he suggested that changes in strength, passion, and reason over the life course are the root cause of the age crime curve.

Claiming something is true and demonstrating it mathematically are two different things. As far as can be determined from a review of the literature, no one has come up with a mathematical formula that can explain the relationship between strength, mental capacity, and criminal propensity. With a little help from germ science, it is suggested that it is possible to develop a mathematical model that provides a plausible explanation for why strength, mental capacity, and criminal propensity are related, and how this relationship creates the age crime curve.

Basic Germ Science

Before proceeding to build a biological explanation for the age crime curve, it will be helpful to look at how toxicity tests are performed on germ cultures. The following description

is a modernized version of the method suggested by Shackell (1925). Let us imagine that a researcher wanted to develop a new disinfectant that kills 99.9% of germs on contact. The researcher is told that the disinfectant can cause cancer in large doses, so the disinfectant must be strong enough to be 99.9% effective at killing germs, but not any stronger than absolutely necessary in order to minimize unwanted side effects. In order to determine the exact amount of disinfectant necessary, the researcher could start by creating a large number of identical germ samples. Then, the researcher could take a series of disinfectant solutions that were increasing in strength by equal amounts ranging from highly diluted to very strong and test the effects on the germ samples. There would be random variation in the results due to variation in the resistance of the germ cultures to the disinfectant. However, the death rates for the germ samples for the various disinfectant strengths could be plotted on a graph to produce a trend line that could be used to determine exactly when 99.9% of the germs would be expected to be killed.

When researchers use the method for testing disinfectant effects on germs that was described above, they often find that the dosage/response curve that describes the relationship between disinfectant strength and the death rate of germs is not a straight line. The typical dosage/response curve is a sigmoid curve as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sigmoid Dosage/Response Curve

Brooks (1918) developed a theory to explain the nonlinear effect of disinfectants on germs. It was suggested that the sigmoid dosage/response curve is created because the resistance of germs to the disinfectant varies over the range of action shown by the sigmoid curve. As the strength of the disinfectant increases linearly, all of the germs that do not have a resistance to that level of disinfectant will die. This effect was called the “law of the minimum” (p. 79). When resistance varies, the resulting dosage/response curve is a sigmoid curve.

Bliss (1935) extended Brooks’ (1918) theory by proposing that the resistance to disinfectants was normally distributed in the germ population. If this were true, then it would be expected that a linear increase in the disinfectant level would be equivalent to a linear increase in the Z-score for a normal distribution. The expected death rate for the germs would be the sum of the probabilities in a normal distribution for all of the germs with a resistance less than that required to withstand that particular level of disinfectant. Bliss did a transformation of the Z-scores for a normal distribution by adding 5 to the Z-score to eliminate negative numbers and called his method, the method of “probits” or “probability units.”

Using the method of probits, it was possible to transform the sigmoid dosage/response curves into straight lines. All that was required was to take the germ death rate for a particular disinfectant level and find the Z-score representing the cumulative probability for a normal curve that matched the death rate. If the researcher added 5 to the Z-score to eliminate negative numbers, the resulting dosage response curve could be plotted as a straight line, greatly simplifying the plotting process. This method became known as “Probit Analysis” (Finney, 1947).

Those familiar with probit analysis may wonder why such a detailed explanation was presented. This extended explanation was provided because most people use probit analysis without considering the theory behind the process. It is suggested that the mathematical relationship between dosage and response has a theoretical basis that has to do with the idea of “capacity.” The capacity of a germ to withstand a disinfectant is normally distributed in the germ population. As the disinfectant level rises linearly, a sigmoid dosage/response curve is the result because all of the germs with a lower capacity to withstand a particular level of disinfectant will die.

This theory did not develop from the contemplation of similarities between germs and criminals. It began with the analysis of criminal propensity scores for a population of criminals on probation (Arnold, 2007). In this study, criminal propensity, which is the risk of a person committing a crime, had been assessed by giving offenders repeated risk assessments at 7 month intervals with the Level of Service Inventory-Revised (LSI-R; Andrews and Bonta, 1995). An

examination of the offender sample's mean level of risk over time indicated that criminal propensity was slowly declining over time at a mean rate of .7 LSI-R points per year. The question was asked, is this gradual reduction in criminal propensity due to the activities of the probation officers, or was it due to the natural decline of criminal propensity in the population of adult offenders due to the effects of aging?

The science of criminology is devoted to the discovery of the causes of criminal behavior. Criminologists study differences and similarities between individuals and also within individuals over time to determine why individuals commit crimes. One of the most important indices of changes in criminal activity that occur within individuals over time is the population age distribution of crime, known as the "age crime curve" (Farrington, 1986). Adolphe Quetelet (1831/1984) was one of the first to study the age crime curve. He analyzed arrest rates in France in the early 1800s for people of various ages and found that there was a curious pattern. Arrest rates were very low for children and then grew to a peak in late adolescence and young adulthood. The rates of arrest by age then started falling almost as rapidly as they had climbed, declining over the life course until few people were arrested for committing crimes in old age. Quetelet (1831/1984; pp. 54-55) proposed a biological explanation for the age distribution of crime that involved strength, passion and reason. Strength and passion were posited to be low in the very young and the very old, and high in adolescence when reason had not yet reached its peak. Crime was proposed to follow the same increasing and decreasing pattern as strength and passion. It was proposed that crime also declined as people moved into adulthood because of the growth of reason with age. Quetelet (1831/1984; p. 55) suggested that there was not sufficient data at that time to test his biological explanation for the age distribution of crime. That situation

has changed somewhat and we now have a much better idea of how strength and reason change over the life course. An attempt will be made in this article to show that Quetelet (1831/1984) was on the right track and that the age crime curve is caused by developmental changes in physical and mental capacity over the life course.

It is now 180 years later, and we know much more about how various human factors such as physical and mental capacity change over the life course. It would seem to be an appropriate time to blow the dust off Quetelet's biological explanation for the age distribution of crime to see if it has any validity. Biological explanations for crime have gained increased acceptance in recent years (Walsh, & Beaver, 2009; Wright, Tibbetts, & Daigle, 2008), and no longer have the stigma that they once did (Rafter, 2008).

The age distribution of arrests has since become known as the "age crime curve" (Farrington, 1986). There has been an increasing level of interest in the age distribution of crime over the past 50 years, beginning with discussions of age and crime by Greenberg (1977), Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983), and Farrington (1986). Although there has been considerable speculation on the reasons for the age crime curve, proposed empirical solutions have been limited. This paper fills a need for further exploration of the proposition that developmental changes in strength and mental ability cause the age crime curve.

The age-crime curve is one of the most well established facts about the distribution of crime in the population (Farrington, 1986, Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). See Figure 1 for the plots of separate age-crime curves for males and females found by calculating the total number

of arrests by age and gender in the United States for the eleven years from 1996 to 2006. It is apparent that the general shapes of the age crime curves for males and females are similar, but that the peak level of crime at age 18 is about four times higher for males than females. To give some perspective on relative numbers, the percentage of male arrested at age 18 is about 6% of all males, and the average level of crimes for females at age 18 is about 5% of all females. Note that crime appears to be nonexistent for the very young and very old, but this is an artifact of the scale differences. Although the numbers of arrests are very low at the ends of the scale, there were non-zero arrest data that ranged from ages 1 to 98.

Although criminologists have been discussing the age crime curve since the 1970s (Farrington, 1986; 1990; Gove, 1985; Greenberg, 1977; 1985; Greenberg, & Larkin, 1985; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983; Steffensmeier, & Allan, 2000; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998), there does not seem to be a generally accepted explanation for the age distribution of crime (Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Sweeten, Piquero, & Steinberg, 2013). It would seem that this is a serious oversight (Loeber, 2012; Osgood, 2005;2012). Without an adequate explanation for the causes of the population distribution of crime by age, it is difficult to identify the between individual differences in normal levels of within-individual variation in crime over the life course. Determining the probable cause of the age crime curve is a conceptual problem that must be solved if progress is to be made in a life course model of criminal activity. If, as this model appears to suggest, physical and mental capacities cause changes in the probability of arrest over the life course, measures of the individual levels of these capacities should be included in any life course studies of crime.

This paper presents a test of Quetelet's biological explanation of the age crime curve. Quetelet proposed that population changes in physical strength, passion, and mental capacity

(reason) over the life course cause the distinctive shape of the age crime curve. Since it would appear that passion and reason are both directly related to mental capacity, a simplified model that only includes life course trajectories of physical and mental capacity will be tested. If additional data on the level of passion can be found, this could be added to the model later.

From an examination of the issues involved, it would appear that increased physical strength or diminished mental capacity are unlikely to cause crime directly. It would appear that the issue is one of capacity. A certain level of physical capacity is required for many crimes to be committed. Therefore, given that strength should be directly related to the level of crime, it seems reasonable that crime increases with increases in physical strength in adolescence and decreases with the declines in strength as people age as Quetelet suggested.

Also, since mental capacity tends to increase with age, it would not seem unreasonable to expect that people would be less likely to commit crimes as intelligence increases due to brain development. There is a well established negative relationship between mental ability and criminal behavior, with crime decreasing as mental ability increases (Wilson, & Hernstein, 1985; Hirschi, & Hindelang, 1977). Given the fact that crime is inversely related to mental capacity, criminal behavior should decrease as intelligence increases from birth to middle age due to increases in brain capacity with age.

An examination of the timing of the growth and decline of physical and mental abilities over the life course provides a challenge to the theorist however. It will be shown that physical capacity peaks in the mid-twenties, and mental capacity peaks in the mid thirties. Crime starts decreasing at about age 18, well before the peak in strength. It would appear that crime should have continued to grow into the mid twenties. In the tests done in this article, it would appear that under certain circumstances, the timing of the growth trajectories of physical and mental

capacities can produce the age crime curve. This would appear to provide some support for Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve.

The data suggests that the age crime curve is a cumulative probability distribution that is driven by changes in strength and brain capacity over the life course. There would appear to be three primary patterns in the age distribution of crime, a childhood pattern from 0-19, a young adult pattern from 19-35, and an older adult pattern from 36-98. As the body gains strength in childhood and adolescence from ages 0-18, and the brain has not yet developed full control, crime increases. From age 19-35, the brain continues to develop, while levels of strength change slowly. This results in a sharp drop in crime from 19 to 30, followed by a gradual flattening of the age crime curve from 30 to 40. As strength starts to decline more rapidly in old age, crime starts to drop off again.

The methods used in this paper fall under the heading of logical inference and exploratory data analysis (EDA; Behrens, 1997; Tukey, 1977). A thorough analysis of the empirical research on crime as well as an analysis of the research on physical and mental development will be conducted to determine a set of logical inferences that appear to flow from the research. These logical inferences will be used to construct a model designed to explain how life course changes in physical and mental capacities might cause the age crime curve.

In conjunction with an analysis of prior research, exploratory data analysis will also be used. EDA provides a set of techniques for analyzing data that include visual inspection of data and graphical analysis. While the results provided by EDA do not provide the type of empirical evidence that is normally associated with tests of theory, it would seem that graphical methods of analysis are probably all that are possible with the types of population data on strength, mental

capacity, and crime that are currently available. The purpose of these analysis is to provide direction for future studies that could explore these hypotheses in more depth.

This article provides several important contributions to the literature on the age crime curve. It will be suggested that the age crime curve is composed of three separate curvilinear trajectories, rather than the two trajectories previously considered. Previous discussions of the age crime curve focus on the fact that crime increases from birth to about age 18 and then decrease from 19 to death. The evidence suggests that there is aa separate transition in the age crime curve from 19-35 that also needs to be explained. Using a three phase model of physical strength and mental capacity, A mathematical model of strength and mental capacity will be developed that shows a high level of ability to predict the age crime curve. It will be demonstrated that the age crime curve appears to be a cumulative probability distribution. The methods used in these analyses do not appear to have been used before in criminology, and so it is possible that they will open up further avenues for research.

The Age Crime Debate

An article by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) appears to have set the stage for much of the later research and discussions on the age distribution of crime. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) proposed three controversial hypotheses, that have come to be known as (1) the “invariance hypothesis,” (2) the “non-interactive hypothesis,” and (3) the “inexplicability hypothesis” (Britt, 1992; Sweeten, Piquero, and Laurence, 2012; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998). These three hypotheses were stated by Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) as follows,

(1) the age distribution of crime is invariant across social and cultural conditions; (2) theories of crime that do not explicitly attend to age have no logical or empirical obligation to do

so and should not be judged by their apparent ability or inability to account for the age effect; (3) the age distribution of crime cannot be accounted for by any variable or combination of variables currently available to criminology; (p. 554)

The biological explanation for the age crime curve proposed by Quetelet is compatible with all three hypothesis. If there is a biological explanation for the age crime curve, the curve should not vary by social and cultural conditions, sociological theories of crime should not have to explain the biological changes across the life course, and sociological variables should not be able to explain biological development. The evidence suggests that there is limited support for these three hypotheses.

The invariance hypothesis

Regarding the invariance hypotheses, the evidence suggests that it is important to define exactly what is meant by the term “invariance.” Britt (1992), citing an unpublished paper by Land, McCall, and Cohen (1989), suggests that the invariance of the age crime curve can consist of either parametric or mathematical forms of invariance. Parametric invariance would require that there is the same mean peak in offending across all cultures. A mathematical form of invariance would simply require that the age-crime curve has the same general mathematical distribution across all cultures. It appears that there is more support for a mathematical form of invariance than there is for parametric invariance.

If the parametric form of invariance were present, there would be a peak in crime at the same mean age across all cultures. This would appear to be an untenable position since the mean age of the peak in criminal activity varies over different time periods and cultures (Farrington, 1986; Greenberg, 1985; 2008; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991). The level of crime also varies widely between countries (United Nations, n.d.),

which provides strong evidence that the height of the age crime probably varies between cultures. These data suggest that the parametric form of invariance does not exist.

The possibility that the age crime curve has the same mathematical form in every culture and time period would appear to be a less controversial proposition (Britt, 1992; Farrington, 1986; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983; Quetelet, 1831/1984; Shavit, & Rattner, 1988; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998; Zhong, 2005). There would appear to be a “unimodal” structure in the age distribution of crime across all cultures, with a peak in crime in late adolescence.

A mathematical form of invariance is compatible with a biological explanation for the age crime curve. Even though there may be changes between cultures in the mean age that crime peaks, or the level of the peak, it is likely that biological factors would still create a single peak in late adolescence.

There is no general consensus on the exact nature of the mathematical form of the age crime curve. Loeber (2012) suggested that the age crime curve is quadratic or cubic. Others (Blumstein, Farrington, & Moitra, 1985; Moffit, 1993) have suggested that the age crime curve is the combination of multiple offending curves. A review of the literature by Jennings and Reingle (2012) provides support for five separate types of offending trajectories that make up the age crime curve. Telesca Erosheva, Kreager, and Matsueda (2012) suggest that the age-crime curve is unimodal, and tried to replicate it with a Poisson warping regression model. Given that lack of consensus in this area, it would appear that any efforts to derive the mathematical form of the age crime curve would be a step in the right direction.

The current test of Quetelet’s biological model is an attempt to provide an explanation for the mathematical form of invariance, which is the invariance of the age crime curve across social

and cultural conditions. The model presented here is a departure from past attempts to provide an explanation for the shape of the age crime curve. Although attempts have been made to find mathematical formulas that might explain the rate of crime over the life course (Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visher, 1986; Nagin, & Land, 1993), and theorists have posited that crime desists in adulthood due to developmental processes (Leblanc, & Loeber, 1998; Loeber, & Leblanc, 1990), it does not appear that there has been an attempt to discover the mathematical relationship between crime rates and changes in physical and mental capacity.

The non-interactive hypothesis

The non-interactive hypothesis is that sociological theories of crime do not have to explain the variation in crime rates with age. Hirschi and Gottfredson (1983) argued that the reasons that different groups commit varying levels of crime is not related to the reasons that people at different ages commit different levels of crime. It is less clear that this hypothesis is compatible with a biological explanation with the age crime curve. If there are time stable differences in the biological capacities for criminal activity, these could create interactions with sociological variables. For instance, if the time varying rate of mental capacity affects the rates of crime, time stable differences may show up as sociological differences such as socioeconomic status. The present exploration does not take these factors into account.

The inexplicability hypothesis

The inexplicability hypothesis is that sociological variables will not explain the age crime curve. A major test of the inexplicability hypothesis was done by Sweeten, Piquero, and Lauritsen (2013). They included up to 40 variables in a multivariate random effects binomial

regression model predicting the level of criminal involvement with age. They used linear and quadratic terms in the model. The sample included subjects that had been convicted of a serious offense from 14 to 18 and followed for several years. They began with a model that included only age, and then added theoretically relevant variables to determine if the age effect could be reduced to zero. If the age variable could be reduced to zero, it would indicate that other sets of variables could explain crime, and thus disprove the inexplicability hypothesis. The age variable could be reduced from explaining 89% of the variation to explaining 21% in the best fitting model. It was suggested that the inexplicability hypothesis could not be disproven completely.

One of the more interesting conclusions was, “The results of our investigation shows that one reason it is so difficult to explain why people stop committing crimes as they get older is that this drop is the result of the combined small effects of many, many factors, and not the result of any one or two specific influences operating alone.” (Sweeten et al., 2013; p. 16) The proposed test of Quetelet’s biological explanation of the age crime curve would appear to refute the conclusion of Sweeten et al. (2013). It would appear that two factors, strength and mental capacity might explain a large portion of the variation in crime rates over the life course.

The current study

The current study will be designed to determine whether population life course trajectories of strength and mental capacity could explain the mathematical form of the age crime curve. This explanation is not designed to explain between individual or within individual changes in crime, although physical strength and mental capacity may affect those differences as well. There are literally hundreds of factors associated with differences in criminal behavior

over the life course (Ellis, Beaver, & Wright, 2009), and it would be illogical to suppose that only two factors affect individual differences in criminal activity.

It is also noted that not all crimes follow the same age crime curve (Greenberg, 1985; Loeber, & Farrington, 2012; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998; Zhong, 2005). Some crimes peak earlier than others, and some peak later. Although the shape of the distribution for individual crimes varies widely, but there is still an overall peak in adolescence for the aggregate level of criminal activity.

There were a number of steps in the development of this biological model of the age crime curve. Some are not intuitive and so there may be some dispute over their validity. Dispute is welcome. A number of basic propositions will be laid out that have varying levels of empirical and logical support. It is suggested that the inevitable conclusion is that there should be certain relationships between the levels of physical strength and mental capacity and the levels of crime by age over the life course. The techniques used to test the empirical model that will be presented have never been used before to my knowledge, and so their validity is subject to debate. The accuracy of the model is so high however, that the accuracy in itself would provide some reason for debate. How can an empirical model fit the data to a ten thousandth of a decimal point if it has no validity?

In the proposal that follows, Quetelet's biological explanation for the shape of the age crime curve will be tested. In testing this explanation, the developmental trajectories of two biological factors, physical strength and brain maturation, will be used to provide a possible explanation for the shape of the age crime curve.

The development of the biological explanation for the age crime curve will consist of three steps. First, a set of logical propositions related to the age crime curve will be discussed.

Second, the dynamics of a general biological explanation for the age crime curve will be explored and some hypotheses will be proposed. Third, a set of predictions will be made and compared with the empirical data on crime.

Some logical propositions

There are several logical propositions that will be made in testing Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve. These propositions are as follows,

- 1) The age crime curve is a population phenomenon.
- 2) The age crime curve must be due to biological factors.
- 3) A single factor biological solution is implausible.
- 4) A two factor biological explanation is the next simplest solution.
- 5) Crimes generally require a certain level of physical capacity.
- 6) Criminal behavior is a poor choice and should be inversely related to mental capacity.
- 5) Crime a social construct, and so analogous behaviors must be considered.
- 6) Rule breaking and aggression decline from birth.
- 7) Criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population
- 8) The age crime curve is a probability distribution.
- 9) There are three separate phases in the age crime curve

The justification for these propositions is discussed below. This will be followed by the presentation of a two factor biological explanation for the age crime curve that addresses these facts. It will be proposed that developmental changes in physical strength interact with developmental changes in the brain to create the age crime curve. A mathematical model will be tested that indicates that there is a strong association between the model and the age crime curve.

The age crime curve is a population phenomenon

The age crime curve is found in the age distribution of arrest rates for the entire population of a country such as the United States (NIBRS, 2012). Some form of the unimodal age crime curve was found in France in the 1800s (Quetelet, 1831/1984), the United States, (NIBRS, 2012), England (Farrington, 1986), and Taiwan (Zhong, 2005). The age crime curve has a similar shape across many periods (Quetelet, 1831/1984; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991), and cultures (Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983). In essence, the age crime curve is most reliably produced when looking at large numbers of people.

Since the age crime curve is a population phenomenon, it cannot be explained by looking solely at subgroups of the population such as criminals. As noted by Durkheim (1895/1938), crime is a normal fact of human behavior. When Quetelet started looking for the causes of crime, he focused on biological traits that were found in all humans, not just a subset of the population.

The fact that different populations have different age crime curves (Zhong, 2005), crime peaks at different ages for different periods or types of crime (Farrington, 1986; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989), or that subgroups of the population have different age crime curves (Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visher, 1986; Ezell, & Cohen, 2005; Glueck, & Glueck, 1950; Jennings, & Reingle, 2012; Moffitt, 1993; Wolfgang, Figlio, & Sellin, 1972) does not negate the fact that there is a general similarity in the age crime curve between populations. Criminal propensity can vary from highly criminal to noncriminal in different groups of people in the population (Moffitt, 1993), but if one limits the analysis of the personal characteristics of the portion of the population that commits the greatest proportion of criminal acts, factors that affect the rest of the population would be ignored.

This is not meant to be a disparagement of attempts to study the age crimes curves of criminals (Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, & Visher, 1986; Sweeten, Piquero, & Lauritsen, 2013). Such efforts are badly needed. It is just that efforts to study criminals are unlikely to provide an insight into the distribution of crime with age for “normal” people.

Any theory that provides an explanation of the age crime curve must use population parameters that vary over time for the entire population as part of the explanation. Whatever is occurring that causes the age crime curve is occurring at the population level for everyone in every population at approximately the same time. The dynamics of the developmental trajectories of the underlying factors that are causing the age crime curve must be identified at the population level in order to explain the generality of the age crime curve across so many locations and time periods.

The age crime curve must be due to biological factors

One of the primary theses of this paper is that the shape of the age crime curve must be due to biological factors. There is considerable support for the invariance hypothesis that the mathematical form of the age crime curve is fairly consistent across cultures and time periods (Britt, 1992; Farrington, 1986; Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990; Hirschi, & Gottfredson, 1983; Quetelet, 1831/1984; Steffensmeier, Allan, Harer, & Streifel, 1989; Steffensmeier, & Streifel, 1991; Tittle, & Grasmick, 1998; Zhong, 2005). These data provide strong evidence that the cause of the age crime curve is biological rather than social. This is not meant to indicate that social factors may not affect the shape of the age crime curve. However social factors must play a secondary role by providing variation from the norm.

Stolzenberg, and D'Alessio (2008) examined the relationship between co-offending and the age-crime curve and found that co-offending did not appear to have a relationship with the

age crime curve. This provides support for the hypothesis that social factors are not causal factors determining the shape of the age crime curve.

Therefore, given that the age-crime curve is found across all cultures, for both sexes, and for various crime types, it is implausible that a sociological explanation is going to provide an adequate explanation of this phenomenon. If sociology cannot explain the age crime curve, then there must be some type of biological explanation.

A single factor biological solution is implausible

In searching for a biological explanation of the age crime curve, It appears that no one single biological factor will be adequate (cf. Gove, 1985). If the shape of the age crime curve shown in Figure 1 is examined, it is clear that the transition from increasing to decreasing crime at about age 18 cannot be due to a single factor. The rapid acceleration in offending behavior seen in adolescence is followed by an almost equally rapid deceleration in offending behavior as the population enters early adulthood. It seems clear that there is no single biological factor that changes that quickly in the population, and so a single factor solution is not possible.

Solutions to the age crime curve such as those proposed by Steinberg (2012) that suggest that changes in brain development alone causes acceleration and declines in criminal activity are untenable, since the speed of changes is not that rapid and the timing of the changes is unequal between individuals. Not every person suddenly develops a brain change exactly at the age of seventeen. There are also slight timing differences in brain development between males and females, and the age crime curves are essentially the same for both sexes (See Figure 2 below). Population level changes in any single biological trait are not as rapid as the acceleration and

decline seen in the age crime curve. This means that an interaction between at least two biological factors is needed to explain the age crime pattern.

An age crime theory should be parsimonious

If a minimum of two factors are needed, more than two factors should be avoided if possible. The principle of Ockham's razor is that the simplest solution that fits the facts should be selected. Sober (1981) called Ockham's principle the "principle of parsimony." Any theory of the age crime curve should use as few variables as it possible. The age crime curve is a population process. Although individual differences in the levels of crime are influenced by thousands of factors (Ellis, Beaver, & Wright, 2009), since the age crime curve is a population phenomenon, one should not need thousands of factors to explain the shape of the age crime curve. It should be possible, through logical examination of population biological dynamics, to find a few simple facts of human development that explain the age relationship between biological changes in the person and the population crime rate by age.

Crimes generally require a certain level of physical capacity

Quetelet (1831) argued that crimes vary over the life course with physical strength. Van De Warker (1875) suggested that the reason crime rates are lower for women is that they have lower levels of physical strength. The evidence presented for this conclusion was that women commit violent crimes, which presumably require more strength, at a rate of 1/6 that of men, while women committed thefts at a rate of 1/4 that of men. While other explanations may account for this difference, difference in physical strength could provide part of the reason that women commit fewer crimes.

Several authors (Adams, 1997; Gove, 1985; Greenberg, 1977) have suggested that physical strength is one factor that affects the level of crime with age. Crimes require a certain level of physical strength and agility, and this factor is changing over the life span. Therefore, it would be reasonable to assume that the amount of strength seen at different ages is related in some fashion to the level of crime committed. Strength levels in the population increase in childhood, remain relatively stable in young adulthood, and then decrease in old age.

Gove (1985) had indicated that the rise and fall of strength is one factor that could play a part in creating the age crime curve. Steffensmeier and Allen (1995) suggested that strength data by age collected by Montoye (1975) indicates that physical strength does not start declining until about age 40 and therefore, declines in strength with age cannot explain the sharp reduction in crime at age 18, as was suggested by Gove (1985). However, this data does not disprove a theory that would propose that the increases in strength from birth to age 18 could cause an increase in crime rates during that period.

In the case of aggression, an increase in strength would explain why, even though overall levels of aggression decline as children age, adolescents are found to be committing more crimes of aggression from 10 to 18. Two 10 year olds hitting each other do little damage, and the police are generally not called to arrest them. Two seventeen year olds hitting each other can do considerable damage and are more likely to be charged with assault. Even though total levels of aggressive behavior are declining from age 10 to 17, there is much more violent crime reported at age 17 than at age 10.

Crime a social construct, and so analogous behaviors must be considered

Crime is a social construct. Crime is defined by the society that a person lives in. Things that are considered crimes vary by the age of the person. For instance, two year old children

regularly bite, hit, and kick each other. These behaviors are not considered crimes for two year olds, and yet they would be considered crimes if an adult performed them. Therefore, any theory that attempts to explain the age crime curve must consider how analogous behaviors vary over the life course.

The two analogous behaviors examined in this paper are rule breaking and aggression. Crime is a form of rule breaking. Crime is a violation of the rules of society. Aggression is also a form of rule breaking. Extremely aggressive acts are sanctioned by the laws in most cultures, although less aggressive acts are not. Crimes are serious violations of the rules of society, and include serious acts of aggression. By looking at how analogous behaviors change over the life course, it is possible to develop explanations that explain why crimes increase from age 10 to 18 while the levels of rule breaking and aggression are declining during that period.

Rule breaking and aggression decline from birth

It may seem counterintuitive when examining the age crime curve, but at the populations level, rule breaking and aggression decline from birth. Logically, if we consider the infant, we find that they do not understand what rules are and do not obey any rules other than those that are biologically imprinted. Children begin life as asocial beings. Therefore, the age of highest rule breaking is at age zero.

Children at the age of two are called the terrible twos for very good reasons. Two year old children are highly self centered and generally are trying to get everyone else to do what they want, rather than doing what others want. With some exceptions, the population pattern is that most children are taught to follow the rules as they age, and continue to be better at following the rules into adulthood.

It would appear that rule following behavior is increasing throughout the entire life course. Since crimes are simply formal rules, and rule breaking began to decline at birth, there

must be something other than the cause of the decline in rule breaking that explains the apparent increase in criminal activity (formal rule breaking) during adolescence.

Several sources confirm the general declines in rule breaking with age. Elliot et al. (1983) examined self report data on criminal activity in adolescence from the National Youth Survey. They found that the prevalence of many crimes was declining from age 11. The incidence of other types of crimes increased during that period, leading to an apparent increase in the overall crime rate with age.

Lauritsen (1998) analyzed longitudinal self report data for criminal activity by adolescents and found that no matter which age from 11 to 17 was used as a starting point, the level of criminal activity declined with age. This data supports the hypothesis that rule breaking is declining at the same time that crime rates appear to be increasing.

Steinberg and Monahan (2007) analyzed age differences in resistance to peer influence using a measure of resistance that was independent of likelihood of engaging in anti-social behavior. They found that resistance to peer influence increases from age 10 through age 23. These data suggest that anti-social peers should have less and less influence with age.

Gottfredson and Hirschi (1990) posited that criminal behavior is more likely if people have low self-control. A review of the research by Pratt and Cullen (2000) provides some support for the theory that low self-control is positively related to criminal activity and analogous behaviors. Turner and Piquero (2002) analyzed the level of self-control within individual adolescents and found that levels of low self-control showed a steady pattern of decreasing levels from ages 9 to 19, which suggests that rule breaking should be decreasing during that period because there is a positive relationship between low self-control and rule breaking.

Similarly, in addition to the declines in rule breaking, aggression appears to be declining from birth as well. Numerous studies suggest that population levels of aggression decline from a young age (Barker et al., 2006; Bongers, Koot, van der Ende, & Verhulst, 2004; Brame, Nagin, & Tremblay, 2001; Broidy, et al., 2003; Nagin & Tremblay, 1999; 2005). While there are generally small groups of children that maintain high levels of aggression or have increases in aggression, the majority of children are exhibiting low stable or declining levels of aggression from a very young age. In general, most people become less aggressive as they age.

These data provide a paradox. Since aggression and rule breaking appear to be declining, something other than an increase in aggression and rule breaking must be causing the increased contact with the criminal justice system. The solution to this paradox requires a reanalysis of what is being reported in official crime rates. It would appear that crime is increasing from 10 to 18, but overall levels of rule breaking and aggression are decreasing. The explanations for this paradox seems to be that either the seriousness of the offenses committed or the official responses to breaking the rules, or both offense seriousness and sanction levels are increasing with age. Acts that are not considered crimes at age 10 are being considered crimes at age 18 either because of the greater strength of the person committing the acts, or the fact that people are more likely to be charged for their actions. It would appear to be difficult to determine which is occurring.

It seems likely that the types of activities performed are changing from childhood to adulthood. This is called heterotypic continuity (Wright, Tibbetts, & Daigle, 2008). With heterotypic continuity, biting at age two turns into hitting at age 18. It is possible that rule breaking can be declining at the population level from ages 0-18, while appearing to increase from 0-18 when measured as criminal acts. Therefore, analogous rule breaking behaviors must

be considered when examining the age crime curve. When they are, it appears that rule breaking is declining as adolescents age rather than increasing.

Criminal behavior is a poor choice

While it is possible to come up with exceptions, in general, crimes are highly irrational acts that result in little benefit for those committing them (cf. Gottfredson, & Hirschi, 1990). Criminal activity has many unwanted potential consequences. Any solution that is proposed for the reasons that crimes are committed should reflect the fact that criminal behavior tends to be a poor choice and criminal acts would not be committed if the person was acting rationally.

The relationship between mental ability and criminal behavior is well documented (Hirschi, & Hindelang, 1977; Wilson, & Herrnstein, 1985). In general, people who commit crimes tend to have lower levels of intelligence than those who do not commit crimes. Wilson and Herrnstein (1985) found that criminal offenders have an average of an 8 point lower IQ when compared to non-criminals.

One of the more obvious biological changes that occurs in human development is the development of decision making ability over time. Quetelet suggested that reason increases with age. Children have little ability to make choices at birth and develop this ability over time. There appears to be a steady gain in the ability of human beings to process information that continues from birth into middle age. The proposition that maturation is a possible reason for a decline in criminal activity was proposed by Glueck, and Glueck (1950; p. 274). In a review of possible reasons for the decline in crime with age, Loeber and Farrington (2012) discuss “brain maturation” as a possible reason.

Any discussion of brain maturation must deal with the fact that the brain is maturing from birth. Why do arrest rates increase in adolescence if the brain is becoming better at making

decisions? One would expect a decrease in rule breaking, and not an increase. As mentioned previously, rule breaking and aggression are decreasing from birth. This is exactly what should happen if rule breaking is a poor choice and the apparatus for making choices, the brain, was improving over time. If overall levels of rule breaking are decreasing from ages 10 to 18, some other reason must be found for the apparent reverse effect of crime increasing in adolescence.

Theoretical explanations of the age crime curve that fail to account for the actual decline in rule breaking from birth are suspect. For instance, Steinberg (2012) fails to take the decline in rule breaking in adolescence into account when arguing that crime increases because adolescents simply do not have the cognitive ability to make decisions like adults. While this is partially true, he fails to account for the fact that cognitive ability is increasing from birth, and rule breaking should be declining. Steinberg (2012) argues that brain changes cause the increase in crime seen in adolescence, and this would not seem to be the case given that aggression and rule breaking are declining from birth. The argument that brain development causes rapid increases and then rapid decreases in crime seems to be contrary to the evidence because brain development is a slow process and changes are not so sudden as to cause the rapid acceleration and deceleration in crime seen at the transition period around age 18.

Criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population

It is proposed that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population. While there is not appear to be a great deal of data to support this claim, there are some discussions on the topic. Clarke and Weisburd (1990) analyzed data from the National Youth Survey that suggests that deviance is more normally distributed when minor forms of deviance are included in the analysis. However, there is a small minority of offenders that tends to skew the deviance distribution in a positive direction. This is consistent with the findings of Wolfgang, Figlio, and

Sellin (1972). Clarke and Weisburd (1990) suggest however, that official reports of deviance such as arrest rates tend to indicate a more normal shape to the distribution of deviance in the population. Since the current study is using arrest data, the proposition that criminal propensity is normally distributed may be warranted. In another study, Wikström (2009) reports that criminal propensity was normally distributed in a random sample of adults assessed in the Peterborough Community Survey. This provides additional support for the proposition that criminal propensity is normally distributed in the population.

The age crime curve is a probability distribution

If one normalizes that age crime curve by turning the number of crimes at each age into a percentage, the age crime curve becomes a probability distribution that provides the probability of arrest at each age. The sum of all of the individual probabilities adds to one. For any arrest, it is possible to calculate the odds of arrest. For instance, if someone is arrested, it can be calculated that there is a 6% chance that they are 18 years old. While this might seem to be a rather useless piece of information, it will become a key part of the model that is proposed.

There are three separate phases in the age crime curve

Previous discussions of the age crime curve have focused on the fact that there are two general trends in the age distribution of crime. Crime increases from childhood to young adulthood and then decreases until death. It is proposed that a two part solution is an oversimplification and that there are actually three phases in the age crime curve. There is a childhood phase from birth to 18, a young adult phase from 19-45, and an older adult phase from 46 to death. The phases are shown in the plots shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Percentages of Crimes by Age for Males and Females (Males = 100%, Females = 100%, Source - NIBRS)

In Figure 2, the United States arrest data from 1996 to 2006 for males and females (NIBRS, 2012) has been transformed into two separate probability distributions. It is clear that the general shape of the curves is fairly similar for males and females. The more obvious transition is seen at age 18, where there is a sharp reversal in the probability of arrest. Crime then declines until about age 30 and then there is another transition phase between ages 30 and 45. These two transitions provide important clues about the processes leading to the age crime curve.

The childhood phase runs from birth to about age eighteen as the child grows from an infant to an adult. There appear to be two sections in this curve, but further analysis will suggest that this is one distinct pattern. There is a period of almost no crime from birth to about age 8 or 9, and then a period of almost linearly increasing crime from about age 10 to 18. It appears on

first examination that the childhood pattern is an exponential growth curve. A later analysis will reveal that this is a more complex cumulative probability distribution from 0-18.

The young adult phase covers the period from 19 to 45. There appears to be a deceleration in the rate of crime that starts rapidly at age 19 and then slowly dissipates in the age range between 30 and 40. The rate of deceleration then starts to increase again at about age 40. The age of 45 is suggested as a cutoff for this range. This deceleration curve is not an exponential curve and it appears to have some interesting properties. This trajectory either fits a cubic model or two quadratic trajectories with the model split at about age 35.

The older adult phase covers the period from 46 to death. There appears to be an exponential deceleration in the rate of crime that starts in the previous section at age 40. Although an initial examination suggests an exponential deceleration curve, further analysis will indicate that this also fits a cumulative probability model.

It will be suggested that these three phases in the age crime curve each require separate explanations. It will be argued that the life course development of physical strength and brain capacity provides a plausible explanation for these three curves. This explanation appears to provide a strong fit with the known facts on the age distribution of crime.

Tying it all together: A two factor biological solution to the age crime curve

The question becomes, is there a simple explanation that uses population level factors related to the biological development of the physical and mental capacities of the individual that would explain the crime and analogous behaviors that produce the age crime curve? It appears that the answer to this question is yes. If the population dynamics of physical strength and brain development are combined, the age crime curve is the result. While this result does not seem immediately intuitive, a thorough examination will reveal that this solution has some merit.

The following argument consists of two primary sets of proposals. The first proposal is that the age crime curve actually consists of three separate curves. There is an acceleration curve in childhood from birth to about age 18, there is a deceleration curve and then an acceleration curve in young adulthood from about 19 to 45, and there is another deceleration curve from about age 46 to death.

The second proposal is that two things are required for a crime to be committed, the physical capacity to commit the crime and a deficiency in the decision making capacity required to prevent the commission of the crime. If there is insufficient physical capacity, or the person has sufficient common sense, crimes generally do not occur. The essence of the theory proposed below is that population timing of developmental changes in physical strength and brain capacity cause the age crime curve.

Changes in Strength with Age

One of the hypotheses of this explanation is that crimes do not occur unless there is sufficient physical strength to commit them. The general pattern seen in the population age strength trajectory is displayed in Figure 3 below. The model shown in Figure 3 is a hypothetical model that is not based on empirical data. The assumptions used in this model are that, at the population level, strength starts at near zero at birth, climbs linearly over most of the childhood years and then peaks in the mid 20s, remains relatively flat until age 40, and then declines linearly with age. While there is not a longitudinal study of strength that covers the entire life course, Malina, Bouchard, and Bar-Or (2004; pp. 218-223) document an almost linear increases in strength from preschool to about age 18, so this part of the model should be relatively accurate.

Figure 3: Hypothesized Strength Level by Age

Figure 4 gives an example of the changes in strength that might be found by using actual data. As shown in Figure 4, using data adapted from Sterken (2001) the average predicted speed correction factors for race distances from 5K to the marathon for ages 1 to 95 follow a similar pattern to the hypothesized pattern in Figure 3. If we assume that running speed is a proxy for strength, we can use this as an approximation for the level of strength by age.

There are some differences between the hypothesized and actual strength data that are worth noting. Strength does not start at zero, as suggested by the hypothesized model. Sterken's (2001) data suggests that one year old racers are moving at 40% of peak velocity, which seems unlikely and suggests that there may be some problems with the model used in that analysis. These problems are minor and should not affect the discussions that follow. The main point is that strength follows a curvilinear trajectory over the life course with near linear increases in youth, peak strength levels occurring somewhere in the mid 20s, and near linear decreases in strength for older adults.

Figure 4: Estimated Speed Correction Factor by Age (Sterken, 2001)

If the strength pattern is compared with the pattern seen in the age crime curve, it would appear that the increases in strength found from age ten to 18 closely mirror the linear increases in crime found during that age period. Similarly, the declines in strength seen from age 35 to 98 also mirror the declines in crime from ages 35 to 98. While it would appear that the strength curve matches the general direction taken by crime rates seen in the first and third section of the age crime curve, the linear nature of the changes in strength do not match the nonlinear changes in the crime rate. This problem will be addressed later.

Changes in Brain Function with Age

It is hypothesized that the avoidance of criminal behavior requires a certain level of decision-making capacity. In that case, rule breaking should be inversely related to the level of decision making capacity. As brain function increases, rule breaking should decrease.

For the purposes of this discussion, it is proposed that the decision-making capacity of the brain starts at a low point and grows over the life course, eventually peaking at about age 30-35, where it flattens out and then begins declining. A hypothetical approximation of the

developmental trajectory of the growth of the decision-making capacity of the brain over the life course is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Hypothesized Level of Brain Capacity with Age

The model in Figure 5 is supported by data collected by Lehman (1953) that shows the intellectual productivity levels for various professions as people age. Functional capacity increases until about age 30 to 40 and then starts to decline in old age. The level of intellectual capacity does not decline to zero in old age.

The suggestion that there was a connection between brain capacity and the age crime curve is not new. Kanazawa (2003) analyzed productivity data for 280 scientists and found that productivity peaked at age 30. Peaks in other types of productivity were found between 35 to 45. In the discussion of the results for productivity, it was noted that crime also peaks and then declines. The fact that both intellectual activity and crime both peak was referred to as the crime-genius connection. The problem with Kanazawa's (2000) arguments is that crime peaks about 10-15 years before intellectual achievement. It will be argued here that the increase in

productivity between age 20 to 35 is caused by the same factors that cause the decrease in crime during that period. The model proposed here is that there is an inverse crime-genius connection.

Changes in the Level of Rule Breaking with Age

It will be proposed that the level of rule breaking is inversely related to the brain's capacity to make decisions. If this is true, we should be able to invert the pattern seen in Figure 5, and the level of rule breaking would follow a trajectory similar to that shown in Figure 6. Rule breaking would be high in infancy and decline with age until about age 30 to 35. Note that if the proposition that rule breaking is inversely related to mental capacity is true, the model predicts that at some point as people age, the level of rule breaking should start to increase again.

It should be noted that in the graph, rule breaking is shown to decrease to zero, which does not happen at age 30 to 35. The zero point simply suggests a minimum level of influence on rule breaking due to brain capacity. The general idea presented is that, if rule breaking is inversely related to brain capacity, a pattern similar to that shown in Figure 6 should be seen in the level of rule breaking over the life course.

Figure 6: Hypothesized Level of Rule Breaking by Age

Combining Strength and Brain Capacity Curves Together in a Z-score Model

How do strength and brain capacity combine to create the age crime curve? It will be suggested that changes in strength and brain capacity creates changes in the Z-score representing the cumulative probability of committing a crime. The logic behind this model came from visualizing what might occur to the Z-score of a criminal propensity distribution if criminal propensity was normally distributed.

The basic Z-score model is shown in Figure 7 below. At various ages the Z-score is either increasing or decreasing. In the example shown in Figure 7, at age 5, the Z-score for the level of strength and brain capacity is -3.96 and increasing. The probability of arrest at age five should be the value of the cumulative probability in a normal distribution for a Z-score of -3.96. This number should be very low since most five-year-old children are not strong enough to commit serious crimes, even though they break many rules. If a linear increase in the Z-score with age occurs, at age 10, the Z-score increases to -2.77. There is a larger cumulative probability of arrest than at age 5, but the total probability of arrest is still low. At age 18, the Z-score increases to -1.55. At age 18, the probability of committing a crime is about 6%, or 6/100ths of the total probability of someone committing a crime at any age. After age 18, as age increases, the Z-score moves back to the left. At age 55, the Z-score is back at the 10-year-old level, and at age 84, the Z-score is at the 5-year-old level.

Figure 7: Probability of Arrest as Age Increases using a Z-Score Model

With this model, the issue then becomes trying to figure out how the Z-score for the criminal propensity probability will change by age. A simple linear model will be proposed. Strength will be considered a risk factor and brain capacity a protective factor. Therefore, the proposed formula for the Z-score is $Z(\text{crime, age}) = F(\text{strength, age}) - G(\text{brain capacity, age})$. Where $F(\text{strength, age})$ is some linear transformation of the mean strength level, and $G(\text{brain capacity, age})$ is a linear transformation of brain capacity.

If linear trajectories for strength and brain capacity are assumed, the following scenario could be imagined. If there was a 5 unit per year increase in the Z-score from 0-18 due to increases in strength, and a 2 unit decrease per year in the Z-score from 0-18 due to increases in brain capacity, the Z-score should rise from near zero at birth at a linear rate of $5 - 2$ units, or 3 units per year until age 18. At that point, the hypothetical Z-score would be 54 units.

The number 54 would not be a number that could be used as a Z-score. If we wanted to use this Z-score with a standard normal probability distribution, the number 54 would have to be

transformed by dividing by a constant and subtracting by another constant to get it into an actual range for a standard normal distribution

It would be difficult to determine the relative amounts of change in the Z-score that is contributed by strength and brain capacity using this process. For instance, strength could increase at 6 units per year, and brain capacity could increase at 3 units, and the resulting increase in the Z-score would still be 3 units per year, just like when strength was increasing by 5 units, and brain capacity was increasing at 2 units. However, this problem aside, the proposed linear Z-score model presents a plausible and testable mathematical model for the process occurring with the Z-scores for the age crime probability distribution.

It will be more important to determine the hypothetical mathematical form of the Z-score distribution if it is a function of strength and brain capacity. It should be possible to do so since the relative changes in strength and brain capacity are well known linear trajectories in childhood from 0-18, and in older adults from 46-98.

Since, strength peaks in the mid twenties and brain capacity peaks in the mid thirties, it would seem clear that in the period from 0-18, strength must be increasing at a faster rate than brain capacity. Since both strength and brain capacity are increasing linearly, there should be a linear increase in the Z-score. To help with the visualization process, the hypothetical trajectories of strength and rule breaking from birth to age 18 are shown in Figure 8. If strength is increasing linearly from 0-18, which leads to an increase in the capacity for crime, and brain capacity is also increasing linearly at a slightly lower rate, then the Z-score by age, which is proposed to be $F(\text{strength, age}) - G(\text{brain capacity, age})$, should increase linearly as well at some rate that is less than the increase in the rate of growth in strength.

Figure 8: Hypothesized Z-score Trajectory Derived from Levels of Strength and Brain Capacity from Birth to 18.

The Z-score model for the likelihood of crime decreasing from age 46-98 should be the reverse of the model for 0-18. In the 46-98 age range, strength is decreasing and brain capacity is decreasing, and it is proposed that crime should decrease at a linear rate as strength declines and brain function declines. In that scenario, the likelihood of committing a crime should decline linearly over time.

The Z-score model for the 19-45 year old range is more complex. Strength is peaking in the mid 20s and brain function is peaking in the mid 30s. The combination of these two curves created by subtracting brain capacity from strength looks something like that shown in Figure 9 below. These curves are not drawn to scale as they tend to look like straight lines at normal scales. If brain capacity levels are subtracted from the strength levels, the Z-score trajectory from 19-45 should be a declining S shaped curve.

Figure 9: Hypothetical Z-score Trajectory Derived from a Combination of Strength and Brain Capacity from 19-45

Using the strength-brain capacity model for the Z-score trajectory results in the Z-score trajectory shown in Figure 10. There is a linear increase in the Z-scores from 0-18, followed by an S shaped section from 19-45, and then an almost linear decrease in the Z-scores from 46-98. This model is shown in relative units. The actual Z-scores would all be negative for the age crime curve. The important point to consider is that the mathematical form of the Z-score model predicted by the actual age crime curve if the strength-brain capacity relationship is accurate would be as shown.

Figure 10: Hypothetical Z-score Trajectory for the Strength-Brain Capacity Model

Testable hypotheses

The preceding model relies on several assumptions. It is assumed that strength is increasing linearly from 0-18, peaking in the mid 20s, remaining relatively flat through the 30s and 40s and then decreasing from 46-98 in an almost linear fashion. Rule breaking is inversely related to brain capacity, and brain capacity is increasing linearly from 0-18, peaking in the mid 30s, at which time it gradually starts to decrease until brain capacity is decreasing from 46-98 in an almost linear fashion. The intersection of strength and rule breaking capacity is a straight line from 0-18 that rises at something less than would be expected if brain capacity were not increasing. The hypothesis for the following analyses is that the combined strength-brain capacity effect should be a linear increase in the Z-score for a criminal propensity normal curve from 0-18, a curvilinear decrease in the Z-score from 19-45, and a linear decrease in the Z-score from 46-98. There should be three sections to the age crime curve, and this model should be able to fit them all. Finally, realistic models for strength and brain capacity should be able to create the age crime curve.

Data and Measures

The age crime curve data used in this article was obtained from the United States National Incident Reporting System (NIBRS, 2012). The arrests in the U.S. for the 11 year period from 1996 through 2006 were downloaded by age, gender, race, and offense category. The data used was limited to age and gender data. The sum of offenses for all 11 years was created for each age. The percentages of offences by age were then computed for both males and females by dividing by the total number of male and female offenses respectively.

Strength and brain capacity measures used to infer the linear trajectories are inferred from a number of sources. There does not appear to be a population level study of either strength or brain functioning that indicates how either changes at the population level over the entire life course. This requires a system of piecing together information. The physical strength and mental capacity curves are a proposed estimate derived from a number of sources.

Malina, Bouchard, and Bar-Or (2004; pp. 218-223) document that the level of strength appears to increase approximately linearly from birth to age 18. Sterken (2001) compiled speed correction data by age for 11 distances from 5K to the marathon for males and females. The speed correction data is used as a proxy for strength.

The dynamic development of intellectual capacity has been studied in a number of ways. Lehman (1953) examined how intellectual productivity varied in a number of professional occupations such as chemistry, philosophy, music, art etc. The general finding was that the level of intellectual capacity peaked somewhere between the ages of 30 to 40. The plot used in the examples were generated from the age crime curve itself. While this plot may be due to other factors, it is approximately representative of the general trend for intellectual development found in other measures.

Procedure

The procedures used in these analyses begin with exploratory data analyses (EDA) using graphical methods as per the suggestions Hartwig, and Dearing (1979). The basic outline of the EDA method was specified by Behrens (1997).

This tradition of EDA can be loosely characterized by (a) an emphasis on the substantive understanding of data that address the broad question of "what is going on here?" (b) an emphasis on graphic representations of data; (c) a focus on tentative model building and hypothesis generation in an iterative process of model specification, residual analysis, and model respecification; (d) use of robust measures, reexpression, and subset analysis; and (e) positions of skepticism, flexibility, and ecumenism regarding which methods to apply. (pp. 131-132)

The basic structure of the age crime curve is apparent from a close examination of the frequency distribution. In addition to the more obvious transition at around age 18, there is also a transition in the mid 30s. This suggested a three-part solution.

The issues with strength and intelligence curves are a bit more complex. While there is no one data set that provides a plot of strength or intelligence curves over the life course, one can construct a general picture by looking at the results from several datasets.

As per suggestions by Behrens (1997), once a hypothesis is generated through exploratory data analysis (EDA), the researcher can use confirmatory data analysis (CFA) to verify the results found. A variety of statistical techniques were used to rule out some solutions and confirm others. Some of the methods used in the analyses that followed required a repeated refinement of manual techniques in Excel as well as repeated tests with statistical analyses software (SPSS, 2009).

Most of the models generated in this test were built in Excel. Two functions, the NormSInv() function, and the NormSDist() functions were used to convert from percentages to Z-scores, and from Z-scores to percentages. Various linear and nonlinear functions were built by summing values over the age distribution from 0-98.

Results and Discussion

Four sets of tests were conducted. The first test was of a linear Z-score model. A linear model was constructed that created linear sets of Z-Scores from 0-18 and from 46-98. The Z-scores were then plotted using the NormSDist() function in Excel and comparing the graphs generated to the actual age crime curves for males and females from the 1996-2006 NIBRS(2012) data. An iterative procedure was used to fit the models to the age crime curves. Three variables, the slope and intercept of the linear Z-score model, as well as a height factor for the percentages generated by the NormSDist() function, were used to adjust the height and shape of the resulting probability distribution. The data for the 19-45 year old age range was generated manually, and so is not part of the test. The standard error and R^2 values were used as a measure of fit and the model was adjusted to find the minimum standard error.

The second test used SPSS curvefit function to generate standard curve formulas to fit the age crime curves for both males and females. The standard error and R^2 values for the various curves were then compared with those of the Z-score model to determine which model provided the best fit with the age crime curve.

The third test used the NormSInv() function to generate a set of Z-Scores directly from the age crime curve data. The 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98 year sections were then examined using curvefit to determine which model might fit the Z-score distribution by age. It is suggested that a three part model fits the age crime curve better than a single or dual section model.

The fourth test involves the two hypothetical sets of data for strength and brain capacity proposed above. The hypothetical curves are combined using the strength-brain capacity formula suggested above, creating a Z-score distribution, and then the hypothetical Z-score distribution is transformed using the NormSDist() function into a hypothetical age crime curve.

Fitting a linear Z-score model to the age crime curve

The goal of the first test was to determine whether a linear change in Z-scores from 0-18 and from 46-98 could explain why the age crime curve rises slowly in childhood and then starts to accelerate in adolescence, and then falls from 46-98 in a gradual deceleration curve. The following procedures were the same for males and females. An Excel spreadsheet was set up with the following rows.

1. Row 1 represented the ages in the age crime curve, and columns were numbered from 0-98.
2. Row 2 was the Z-score row, which was set up to house the predicted Z-scores from 0-98. Predicted Z-scores were generated by a slope(b)-intercept(a) pair for a line with formula $Z = a + bX$ for ages 0-18 and ages 46-98. Ages 19-46 were fitted manually.
3. Row 3 contained the predicted probability for each Z-score for a normal distribution with mean 0, and standard deviation of 1. Row 3 was populated by using the NormSDist() function with Row 2 as the source for X. The NormSDist() function produces the cumulative probability for a Z-score value assuming a normal distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation of 1.
4. Row 4 contained the cumulative probabilities in Row 3 divided by a constant. The constant was used to adjust the height of the predicted age crime curve.
5. Row 5 contained the actual age crime curve percentages from the average U.S. crime rates from 1996-2006 (NIBRS, 2012) for either males or females.
6. Row 6 contained the difference between the adjusted predicted values (Row 4) and the actual values (Row 5).

7. Row 7 contained the square of the differences between the predicted and actual values (Row 6). The sum of sections of this row provided the sum of the squares that was used to calculate standard errors and R^2 values.
8. A graph was set up to display the predicted values (Row 4) and the actual values (Row 5) of the age crime curve.
9. A control section was set up to house the slope-intercept values for the 0-18 and 46-98 sections, the single divisor for the height adjustment, and the standard errors and R^2 values for each section and the total.

The slope, intercept, and divisor were adjusted for the 0-18 Z-score values until a close match was obtained with the first section of the age crime curve. Z-scores were entered manually for each year from 19-45 to minimize the difference between the calculated probability and the actual age crime curve value. Finally, the slope and intercepts were entered for the age range from 46-98. The results are shown in Figures 12 and 13. Figure 12 shows a plot of the projected and actual age crime curves for males, and Figure 13 shows a plot of the actual and projected age crime curves for females. The fit between the models and the actual age crime curves for both males and females is almost perfect.

Figure 12: Projected and Actual Age Crime Curves for Males

Figure 13: Projected and Actual Age Crime Curves for Females

The model parameters and model fit statistics for males and females are shown in Table 1. These data indicate a very close fit between the hypothetical Z-score model predicted by the strength-brain capacity relationship and the average 1996-2006 age crime curves. The R^2 values are very close to 1, indicating an almost perfect fit between the models and the actual age crime curves. Note that the fit from 19-45 was done manually, so the errors for that range are artificially low.

The predicted values for the 0-18 and 46-96 ranges are very close to the actual values. These data provide strong support for a linear Z-score model for these two age ranges.

Whether this fit is due to levels of strength minus levels of brain capacity would still need to be determined. However, it does appear that crime rates are compatible with the trajectories of strength and brain capacity if a linear trajectory is assumed for these physical factors in the age ranges from 0-18 and from 46-98.

Table 1: Model Parameters and Fit Statistics for the Z-Score Model of the Age Crime Curve

Model	Age Range			
	0-18	19-45	46-98	Total (0-98)
Males				
Intercept (a)	-5.0100		-1.0700	
Slope (b)	.3352		.0760	
Divisor	13.7760			
S.E.	.000478	.000052	.000217	.000528
R^2	.999643	.999997	.998028	.999836
Females				
Intercept (a)	-7.2000		-.9000	
Slope (b)	.5500		.0870	
Divisor	19.4000			
S.E.	.000459	.000002	.000158	.000228
R^2	.999497	1.000000	.995001	.999736

Testing other types of curves against the Z-score model

The Z-score models for males and females appeared to have an excellent fit with the actual age crime curves. It is not clear however, that some other model might not provide as close a match as the Z-score model. Therefore, a number of other models were tested. In the tests that followed, the model fit for various mathematical formulas was tested against the individual age crime curves for the 11 years from 1996-2006, rather than the average curves that had been generated. Testing against the 11 individual annual curves would introduce more variation into the test and this would appear to provide a more accurate test of the model's abilities to predict the age crime curve.

The SPSS curvefit command was used to try to find a formula to fit the entire age crime curve and then the sections of the age crime curve from 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98. All available curve types were tested, which included linear, logarithmic, inverse, quadratic, cubic, compound, power, S, growth, exponential, and logistic fit solutions.

In the full 0-98 year age crime curve model, logarithmic, inverse, power, and S curves had a low R^2 values and so they were not examined further. Compound, growth, exponential, and logistic models all had identical R^2 values, so the growth curve was used to represent that type of curve. The tested curves for the full 0-98 model were reduced to linear, quadratic, cubic, and exponential. The models and R^2 values are shown for the single curve solutions compared to the three part Z-score model in Table 2. It seems clear that the Z-score model is a far more accurate model. Even with the extra variation introduced by comparing the Z-score model to all 11 years, the Z-score model R^2 is .987

Table 2: Single Curve Fit Solutions compared to the Three Part Z-score Model

Model	Formula	a	b ₁	b ₂	b ₃	R ²
Males						
Linear	$Y=a + b_1X$.0242	-.000283			.305
Quadratic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2$.0185	.000061	-.00000348		.335
Cubic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2 + b_3X^3$	-.0036	.002672	-.00006908	.00000044	.628
Growth	$Y=e^{(a + b_1X)}$	-3.450	-.072967			.352
Z-score	$Y=a_1*\sum e^{(a_2+b_1X)^2}$.987
Females						
Linear	$Y=a + b_1X$.0242	-.000283			.323
Quadratic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2$.0183	.000071	-.00000357		.356
Cubic	$Y=a + b_1X + b_2X^2 + b_3X^3$	-.0039	.002690	-.00006937	.00000044	.669
Growth	$Y=e^{(a + b_1X)}$	-3.6174	-.075643			.284
Z-score	$Y=a_1*\sum e^{(a_2+b_1X)^2}$.987

The single solution curves for male arrest rates were plotted along with the three part Z-score model in Figure 14. The other curves do not come close to producing a plot similar to the age crime curve. This suggests that a single curve solution is not possible with simple mathematical models.

Figure 14: Male Single Curve Fit Solutions compared to the Three Part Z-score Model

Two and Three Section Age Crime Curve Models

The single curve solutions had a poor fit to the age crime curve. Two and three part models were tested by dividing the age crime curve data into two sections from 0-18, and 19-98, and three sections, 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98. The SPSS curve fit procedure was run for males and females for both the two section and three section models.

Different curve types had better fits depending on the section being tested. Compound, growth, exponential, and logistic models all had identical R^2 values, so the growth curve was used to represent that type of curve. This left linear, logarithmic, inverse, quadratic, cubic, power, S, and exponential fit solutions. The R^2 values for these models are presented in Table 3 below along with the explained variance for the Z-score model.

Table 3: Explained Variance for Section Models and Total Age Crime Curve Models

Model	0-18	19-45	46-98	19-98	Total (0-98)
Males					
Linear	.744	.758	.541	.727	.305
Logarithmic	.449	.826	.622	.871	.091
Inverse	.173	.883	.702	.951	.003
Quadratic	.967	.878	.837	.943	.335
Cubic	.973	.878	.837	.956	.628
Power	.855	.890	.787	.739	.044
S	.510	.902	.740	.576	.036
Growth	.911	.862	.822	.857	.352
Z-score	.982	.964	.939	.990	.987
Females					
Linear	.766	.777	.512	.760	.323
Logarithmic	.476	.814	.592	.887	.095
Inverse	.187	.841	.671	.933	.003
Quadratic	.933	.811	.805	.953	.356
Cubic	.936	.811	.805	.955	.669
Power	.795	.782	.704	.680	.023
S	.482	.763	.654	.521	.053
Growth	.824	.789	.745	.800	.284
Z-score	.983	.935	.924	.989	.987

These data suggest that the age crime curve is probably some type of cumulative probability function. The other types of mathematical models have fairly high R^2 values, but visual inspection reveals that they do not fit the actual age crime curve data. The highest R^2 values are found with the Z-score model in every case. Note that the section from 19-45 was fit by hand, and so this is not a fair test, but both the 0-18, and 46-98 year old sections are simple linear fit predictions that assume a linear Z-score model in these sections.

The mathematical form of the function for the 0-18 and 46-98 year olds is $Y=a_1*\sum e^{(a_2+b_1X)^2}$. The function in the parenthesis is linear. It is not clear what the function is for the 19-45 year olds. It would appear to be some type of nonlinear function. In the next section, an attempt will be made to determine the mathematical form of all three sections.

Determining the mathematical form of the age crime curve Z-score distribution

The preceding analyses suggested that the age crime curve was some stype of cumulative probability function. If the physical and mental capacities with presumed to affect the Z-score, and the Z-score followed a linear trajectory, it was possible to build a very accurate mathematical model that predicted the arrest rate by age. The NormSDist() function in Excel was used to convert Z-scores to probabilities.

It is also possible to work backward. The NormSInv() function in Excel can convert probabilities to Z-scores. This provides a method for converting the age crime curve to a Z-score distribution without all of the manual fitting required to build the model shown above. It would then be possible to examine each Z-score section to determine what type of mathematical form it had. It would be possible to determine whether the sections from 0-18 and 46-96 were actually linear functions. Creating a Z-score distribution using actual data would also provide a way to try to find the mathematical properties of the Z-score distribution from 19-46.

A simple Excel spreadsheet was created with the age from 0-98 in Row 1, the Age Crime Curve from 1-98 in Row 2, and a Z-score transformation in Row 3 that was created by the NormSInv() function with the values in Row 2 used for X. The Z-score distribution shown in Table 14 was generated. This graph shows the Z-score distribution for males and females. The data for ages 1-2 and from 94-98 appears to not fit the pattern, but the rest of the data seems to indicate a consistent process. Z-scores appear to range from -1.5 to -4.5.

Figure 15: Z-scores for Male and Female Age Crime Curve

One interesting feature of the comparison plots in Figure 15 is that males tend to have slightly higher Z-scores than females before age 10, and then have lower Z-scores from 10-18. This could be due to earlier physical maturation in young male children and earlier puberty and physical maturation by female adolescents.

The Z-Scores for males for the years 1996 to 2006 were plotted for the three sections from 0-18, 19-45, and 46-98 in Figures 16, 17, and 18. Note that the graphs are not all drawn to the same scale. There were missing values in the 1-3 and 94-98 age ranges. These cells were set

to the closest value that was not missing to prevent the plots from having large swings. Since the values in these cells were close to zero, this does not substantially affect the plots.

The 0-18 age range shown in Figure 16 shows that the Z-score trajectory appears to fit a linear pattern from ages 3 to 15. Ages 1 and 2 have little data and are unreliable. From ages 16 to 18 there appears to be a gradual deceleration in the rate of increase. It is not clear if the deceleration from 16 to 18 is due to the process occurring from ages 3-15 slowing down, or if this is due to the process that is occurring from 19 to 30 starting to have an effect.

A curvefit test was run in SPSS for the age range from 3-15. The linear model R² values were high (male R² = .976, female R² = .972), and the cubic model R² for males or females added less than .005 to the R² value. This does not appear to be strong evidence against a linear increase in the process creating the age crime curve from 3-15.

Figure 16: Z-scores for Male Age Crime Curve for 0-18 Year Olds (1996-2006)

The Z-score trajectory for the 19-45 year old age range is shown in Figure 17. The Z-score trajectory in this age range appears to fit a cubic model. There is a gradual deceleration curve from 19 to 30, and then a transition period from 30 to 45, followed by a steady decline from about age 45 onward. In subsequent analyses, this section will be split into two parts at age 35 in order to get a more precise picture of what is occurring.

Figure 17: Z-scores for Male Age Crime Curve for 19-45 Year Olds (1996-2006)

Figure 18: Z-scores for Male Age Crime Curve for 46-98 Year Olds (1996-2006)

The Z-score trajectory for the age 46 to 98 year old age range is shown in Figure 18. This section of the age crime curve appears to fit a linear model. The Z-scores appear to be declining at a steady rate each year. There might be a slight wave in the line, but any deviation from a linear model is minimal. A cubic model provided an R^2 value that was .001 higher than the linear model for both males and females when the curvefit procedure was used on Z-scores in the age range from 46-93. This does not seem a theoretically relevant improvement in accuracy.

In order to provide some idea of the relative magnitudes of the change in Z-score for males and females, the values of the model coefficients are shown below. While there do not appear to be major differences between the models, the reader should be cautioned the probabilities generated by Z-scores are very sensitive to small changes in magnitude.

Table 4: Z-Score Models for Selected Age Ranges

Ages	Model	a	b ₁	b ₂	R ²
Males					
3-15	Linear	-5.015	.224		.976
19-35	Quadrati c	.405	-.150	.002	.948
36-45	c	-4.855	.159	-.002	.731
46-93	Linear	-.391	-.043		.982
Females					
3-15	Linear	-5.223	.241		.972
19-35	Quadrati c	-.009	-.128	.002	.902

Fitting Hypothetical Strength and Brain Capacity Curve to the Z-score Model

It had been proposed that the strength and brain capacity levels over the life course were operating in opposing directions to create the Z-score trajectory for the age crime curve. As

strength increased, the Z-score for the age crime curve should increase, and as brain capacity increased, the Z-score for the age crime curve should decrease by an equal amount. In this section, this proposition will be tested to see if hypothetical strength and brain capacity curves could create the Z-score distribution for the age crime curve.

The mathematical form of the relationship between the Z-score and the strength and brain capacity levels should be as follows.

$$Z(\text{crime, age}) = a + b * (c * P(\text{strength, age}) - d * P(\text{brain, age}))$$

Where a,b,c, & d are constants

Some simple assumptions were made to create the following strength and brain capacity plots.

1. Strength and brain capacity are changing in a linear fashion in childhood and old age.
2. Strength peaks at age 25 and brain capacity peaks at age 30
3. There is a gradual transition between growth and decline
4. Declines in capacity are slower than the growth of capacity

Using these assumptions and a considerable amount of trial and error, the following two hypothetical curves for strength and brain capacity shown in Figure 19 were developed.

To develop the models shown, positive numbers were used to simplify the visualization process. Linear formulas were used to generate the ascending trajectories for strength and brain capacity. $\text{Capacity}_{(\text{age})} = \text{Capacity}_{(\text{age}-1)} + \text{Constant}$. It was assumed that there could be a slight acceleration in the decline with age, and so the decline curves were of the form $\text{Capacity}(\text{age}) = \text{Capacity}_{(\text{age}-1)} - \text{Constant} - \text{Constant} * (\text{age} - \text{zero age})$. Zero age was 25 for strength and 30 for brain capacity.

Figure 19: Hypothetical Strength and Brain Capacity Curves

At the transition between growth and decline, rounding factors were used to create a gradual transition. For instance, the constant growth factors at each successive year for the strength curve, starting at age 16 were multiplied by .9, .8, .7, etc. until the growth slowed to zero at age 25. Similarly, the decline was started gradually as well by multiplying the successive decline constant factors by .1, .2, .3, ..., 1.

Once the curves shown were generated, using simple addition, the level of brain capacity was subtracted from the level of strength at each year of age. The result was a score that was multiplied by a constant. Finally, 5.1 was subtracted from the total to provide the Z-score. The result was plotted along with the male Z-score trajectory to determine if the model could reproduce the age crime curve. The projected Z-score model generated from the hypothetical strength and brain capacity curves in Figure 19 is shown in Figure 20 along with the actual Z-score trajectory for males.

Figure 20: Projected Z-score Trajectory vs. Actual Age Crime Curve Z-scores for Males

There is not an exact match between the projected and actual Z-scores, but the model uses very simple assumptions. The strength and brain capacity trajectories are set up with similar formulas with only the constants being adjusted in the 0-15 and 46-98 age ranges. The transitions are smooth transitions with little custom manipulation.

The resulting projected age crime curve model is shown in Figure 21. To sum up the process that was used, the strength and brain capacity curves generated in Figure 19, are combined by subtracting brain capacity from strength levels, to generate the Z-score trajectory in Figure 20, which then is transformed using the NormSDist() function in Excel to generate the projected age crime curve in Figure 21. There is a correspondence between all three sets of trajectories.

Figure 20: Projected vs. Actual Male age Crime Curve

Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to test Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve. Quetelet proposed that changes in strength, passion, and reason over the life course were responsible for the age distribution of crime. Quetelet's model was simplified to an analysis of two trajectories, developmental changes in strength and brain development, because it appeared that changes in passion and reason were both caused by brain development. While the results of these analyses do not prove that changes in strength and brain capacity cause the age crime curve, the results demonstrate that biological development of strength and brain capacity could explain the age crime curve. If strength and brain capacity trajectories are combined, they appear to produce the Z-score trajectory for the age crime curve.

In developing the tests that were used, several logical inferences were made. The age crime curve is a population phenomenon and therefore it should be the result of changes in population parameters. The population parameters must be biological since the age crime curve

has a similar shape across cultures and social conditions. There must be a minimum of two biological processes, because the sharp inflection at age 18 could not be the result of changes in a single biological process. The most parsimonious theory should not use more than two biological factors to explain the age crime curve. Since it takes strength to commit a crime and mental capacity to avoid committing crimes, it was proposed that, as Quetelet proposed, strength and brain capacity are logical candidates for the processes that cause the age crime curve. Since crime should be directly related to crime levels, and brain capacity should be inversely related to crime levels, the age crime curve should be the result of some type of mathematical function that changes positively with changes in strength and negatively with changes in brain capacity. It was proposed that the level of strength, minus the level of brain capacity, should generate a Z-score trajectory that would create the age crime curve by adjusting the cumulative probability of criminal activity by age.

A preliminary examination of the age crime curve revealed that the age crime curve appeared to be composed of three separate sections. The sections ranged from ages 0-18, 19-35, and 36-98. Any model that was developed should fit these three sections.

An analysis of the life course trajectories of physical strength and mental capacity revealed the following. Physical strength increases from birth, peaks in the mid 20s, and declines in old age. Mental ability increases from birth, peaks in the mid 30s, and declines in old age. If it is assumed that rule breaking has a negative relationship with mental capacity, it is possible that the strength and brain development trajectories intersect to produce the age crime curves.

Given that both strength and brain capacity trajectories are changing in an approximately linear trajectory from 0-18 and from 46 to 98, it was postulated that there should be a linear

change in the Z-score trajectory underlying the age crime curve for these age ranges. Criminal propensity should increase with increases in strength and decline with increases in brain capacity. A Z-score model is a reasonable premise if the distribution of criminal propensity is distributed normally in the population.

A mathematical model was set up using linear formulas for ages 0-18 and 46-98 to generate Z-score trajectories for males and females and it was found that the models were able to reproduce the age crime curve with a high degree of accuracy. The explained variance against the average age crime curve trajectory was 99.9% for both the male and female models.

In a separate analysis, several other types of curves were generated in SPSS and compared with the projected cumulative probability distribution, that had been created with linear Z-score trajectories from 0-18, and 46-98. The projected age crime curve was superior to the SPSS generated curves and fit the data with the highest level of explained variance, explaining 92.4% to 98.3% of the variation in the sections.

In a further analysis, the age crime curve was transformed into a Z-score trajectory and the resulting Z-score trajectory was analyzed. A linear model was able to explain a high percentage of the variation in the Z-score sections from ages 3-15, and 46-98. The section from 19-35 appeared to fit a quadratic trajectory. The fit for any type of curve for the 36-45 year old data was not as good, suggesting that there was much more variation in this section.

In the final analysis, hypothetical curves for strength and brain capacity by age were generated. The predicted mathematical solution was that strength would positively add to the Z-score level for the age crime curve, and brain capacity would subtract from the Z-score level. It was demonstrated that the hypothetical strength and brain capacity curves could generate the age crime curve with a fair degree of accuracy.

The conclusions that can be derived from these findings appear to be as follows.

1. The age crime curve appears to be a cumulative probability distribution.
2. The Z-score trajectory for the age crime curve follows a linear trajectory from 0-18, a curvilinear trajectory from 19-45, and a linear trajectory from 46-98.
3. The results found are not incompatible with Quetelet's biological explanation for the age crime curve.

These conclusions will be discussed in depth in the sections that follow.

The age crime curve appears to be a cumulative probability distribution

One of the problems researchers have had with attempts to study the age crime curve was that there has been no consensus over the mathematical form of the age crime curve (Britt, 1992). The general consensus has been that there was a mixture of curves that all came together to create the age crime curve. The mixture approach was used by Blumstein, Cohen, Roth, and Visher (1986) in their research on criminal careers, Moffitt (1993) in her adolescent limited/life course persistent model, Laub and Sampson (2003) when looking at life course trajectories, and more recently by Sweeten, Piquero, and Steinberg (2013) when trying to fit a number of theoretically relevant variables to the age crime curve. Sweeten et al. (2013) concluded that it was highly unlikely that one or two variables operating alone could create the age crime curve.

The models developed here suggest that there appears to be support for the proposition that the age crime curve is a cumulative probability distribution of some type. It is possible that this curve could be driven by just two variables. This, in and of itself, would seem to be a significant finding.

The age crime curve is a three-part process

A cumulative probability distribution with age as a linear factor for the Z-scores fits the age crime almost perfectly from 0-18, and from 46-98. At least one other factor would be needed to fit the section of the age crime curve from 19-45. There would appear to be support for the hypothesis that the age crime curve has three sections.

Changes in strength and mental capacity could explain the age crime curve

While correlation does not prove causation, the data is consistent with Quetelet's proposition that strength and reason are important biological factors underlying the age crime curve. These data suggest that the age crime curve in the periods 0-18 and 46-98 is consistent with the hypothesis that the age crime curve is caused by changes in strength and brain capacity, since these biological factors change almost linearly in these age ranges.

It should be noted that many other biological factors also change linearly. For instance, height changes at a linear rate for most of the childhood years (Kuczmarski, Ogden, Guo, et al. 2000).. It should be noted that height does not decline linearly from 46-98, which would then require a separate explanation, which runs afoul of the parsimony rule.

If the reduction in the crime rate from 19-45 was due to increases in brain capacity, it would be expected that the decrease in arrest rates should flatten out in the mid thirties. This hypothesis also appeared to have some empirical support. Arrest rates drop from 19-30 and flatten out for a few years, reaching a minimum at about age 35, when mental capacity is at its peak. The arrest rates then begins to increase slightly before beginning to decline again at about age 40 when strength begins to decline.

Implications for future research

The analyses presented leave many questions unanswered. The model fit is very high, which suggests that the age crime distribution could be caused by changes in strength and age. However, it is not clear that the proposed trajectories are the actual trajectories of strength and crime. The model is very simple, but other factors could cause the age crime curve.

The actual strength trajectory should be measured to see when the changes in strength occur. This could be problematic however, since there are many ways to measure strength. Changes in speed by distance runners was presented as one method, but there are numerous other measures as well. Is there one type of strength that is more important than others?

Would there be inter-individual differences in the rate of crime by level of strength? This is an area that has had very little empirical study. This is rather odd since, as Adams (1997; p. 312) noted, the connection between strength and certain types of crimes is “obvious.”

Glueck and Glueck (1950; 1956), in one of the few studies that attempted to match physical strength characteristics with criminal activity, found that criminal offenders tended to have mesomorphic, or “muscular” body types. However, it is not clear that this applies to the current analyses, since muscular and strong could be different things. Sampson and Laub (1997) reanalyzed the mesomorphy data and suggested that mesomorphy did not predict future criminal behavior. In Quetelet’s explanation, strength is only a factor explaining the instantaneous level of crime, and not future crime.

The Mathematical Form of the Age Crime Curve

The cumulative distribution function of a normal curve is an integral function with the following formula.

References

- Adams, Kenneth G. (1997). Developmental aspects of adult crime. in *Advances in Criminological Theory*, Vol. 7 - Developmental Theories of Crime and Delinquency, edited by Terence Thornberry. New Brunswick, NJ: Transaction Press, pp. 309-342.
- Agnew, Robert, & White, Helene Raskin (1992). An Empirical Test of General Strain Theory. *Criminology*, 30(4): 475-499.
- Baldwin, John D. (1985). Thrill and Adventure Seeking and the Age Distribution of Crime: Comment on Hirschi and Gottfredson. *American Journal of Sociology*, 90(6): 1326-1330.
- Barker, Edward D., Tremblay, Richard E., Nagin, Daniel S., Vitaro, Frank, & Lacourse, Eric (2006). Development of male proactive and reactive physical aggression during adolescence. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 47(8): 783-790.
- Behrens, John T. (1997). Principles and Procedures of Exploratory Data Analysis. *Psychological Methods*, 2(2): 131-160.
- Blumstein, Alfred, Cohen, Jacqueline, & Farrington, David P. (1988a). Criminal career research: Its value for criminology. *Criminology* 26(1): 1-35.
- Blumstein, Alfred, Cohen, Jacqueline, & Farrington, David P. (1988b). Longitudinal and criminal career research : Further clarifications. *Criminology* 26(1): 57-74.
- Blumstein, Alfred, Cohen, Jacqueline, Roth, Jeffrey, & Visher, Christy A. (1986). *Criminal careers and career criminals*, Vol. 1. Washington, DC: National Academy Press.
- Blumstein, Alfred, Farrington, David F., & Moitra, Soumyo (1985). Delinquency Careers: Innocents, Desisters, and Persisters. *Crime and Justice*, 6: 187-219.
- Blumstein, Alfred, Cohen, Jacqueline, & Farrington, David P. (1988a). Criminal career research: Its value for criminology. *Criminology* 26(1): 1-35.

- Blumstein, Alfred, Cohen, Jacqueline, & Farrington, David P. (1988b). Longitudinal and criminal career research : Further clarifications. *Criminology* 26(1): 57-74.
- Boehner, Philotheus (1957). *Ockham: Philosophical Writings*. Edinburgh: Thomas Nelson and Sons, Ltd.
- Bongers, Ilja L., Koot, Hans M., van der Ende, Jan, & Verhulst, Frank C. (2004) Developmental Trajectories of Externalizing Behaviors in Childhood and Adolescence, *Child Development*, 75(5): 1523-1537.
- Brame, Bobby, Nagin, Daniel S., & Tremblay, Richard E. (2001). Developmental Trajectories of Physical Aggression from School Entry to Late Adolescence. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 42(4): 503-512.
- Britt, Chester L. III (1992). Constancy and Change in the U.S. Age Distribution of Crime: A Test of the "Invariance Hypothesis." *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*, (2): 175-187.
- Broidy, Lisa M., Nagin, Daniel S., Tremblay, Richard E., Bates, John E., Brame, Bobby, Dodge, Kenneth A., ... Vitaro, Frank (2003). Developmental Trajectories of Childhood
- Brown, Elizabeth, & Males, Mike (2011). Does age or poverty level best predict criminal arrest and homicide rates? A preliminary investigation. *Justice Policy Journal*, 8(1): 1–30.
- Brooks, S. C. (1918). A Theory of the Mechanism of Disinfection, Hemolysis, and Similar Processes. *The Journal of General Physiology*., 1(1): 61-80.
- Disruptive Behaviors and Adolescent Delinquency: A Six-Site, Cross-National Study. *Developmental Psychology*, 39(2): 222–245.
- Burton, Velmer S., Jr., Cullen, Francis T., Evans, T. David, & Dunaway, R. Gregory (1994). Reconsidering Strain Theory: Operationalization, Rival Theories, and Adult Criminality. *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*, 10(3): 213-239.

- Caspi, Avshalom, Moffitt, Terrie E., Silva, Phil A., Stouthamer-Loeber, Magda, Krueger, Robert F., & Schmutte, Pamela S. (1994). Are some people crime prone? Replications of the personality-crime relation across nation, gender, race and method. *Criminology*, 32(2): 301-333.
- Cauffman, Elizabeth, & Steinberg, Laurence (2000). (Im)maturity of judgment in adolescence: Why adolescent may be less culpable than adults. *Behavioral Sciences and the Law*, 18: 1-21.
- Clarke, Ronald V., & Weisburd, David L. (1990). On the Distribution of Deviance, In Don M Gottfredson and Ronald V Clarke, eds., *Policy and Theory in Criminal Justice*, pp 10-27, Aldershot, England: Gower Publishing Company.
- Durkheim, Emile (1895/1938). *The Rules of Sociological Method* (8th ed.), translated by Sarah A. Solovay and John H. Mueller and edited by George E. G. Catlin. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Ellis, Lee, Beaver, Kevin M., & Wright, John P. (2009). *Handbook of Crime Correlates*. New York: Elsevier.
- Ellis, Lee & Walsh, Anthony (2000). *Criminology: a global perspective*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- Elliott, Delbert S., Ageton, Suzanne S., Huizinga, David H., Knowles, Brian A., & Canter, Rachelle J. (1983). *The Prevalence and Incidence of Delinquent Behavior: 1976-1980*. Boulder, CO: Behavioral Research Institute.
- Ezell, Michael E., & Cohen, Lawrence E. (2005). *Desisting from Crime: Continuity and Change in Long-Term Crime Patterns of Serious Chronic Offenders*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Farrington, David P. (1986). Age and Crime. In M. Tonry & N. Morris (Eds.), *Crime and Justice: An Annual Review of Research* (Vol. 7, pp. 189-250). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Farrington, D. P. (1990). Age, Period, Cohort and Offending. in Gottfredson, D.M and Clarke, R.V. (Eds) *Policy and Theory in Criminal Justice* , 51-75, Aldershot: Avebury.
- Farrington, David P. (2003). Developmental and life-course criminology: Key theoretical and empirical issues – the 2002 Sutherland Award Address. *Criminology*, 41(2): 221- 256.
- Finney, D. J. (1947). *Probit Analysis: A statistical treatment of the sigmoid response curve*. Cambridge, England, Cambridge University Press.
- Giordano, Peggy C., Cernkovich, Stephen A., & Rudolph, Jennifer L. (2002). Gender, crime, and desistance: Toward a theory of cognitive transformation. *American Journal of Sociology*, 107(4): 990–1064.
- Glueck, Sheldon, & Glueck, Eleanor (1937). *Later Criminal Careers*. New York: The Commonwealth Fund.
- Glueck, Sheldon, & Glueck, Eleanor (1950). *Unraveling Juvenile Delinquency*. New York: The Commonwealth Fund.
- Glueck, Sheldon, & Glueck, Eleanor (1956). *Physique and delinquency*. Oxford, England: Harper & Bros.
- Goring, Charles (1913). *The English Convict*. London: His Majesty's Stationery Office.
- Gottfredson, Michael R., & Hirschi, Travis (1986). The True Value of Lambda Would Appear to Be Zero. *Criminology*, 24(2): 213-234.
- Gottfredson, Michael, & Hirschi, Travis (1987). The Methodological Adequacy of Longitudinal Research on Crime," *Criminology* 25(3): 581-614.

- Gottfredson, Michael R., & Hirschi, Travis (1988). Science, public policy, and the career paradigm. *Criminology* 26(1): 37-55.
- Gottfredson, Michael R., & Hirschi, Travis (1990). *A general theory of crime*. Palo Alto, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Gove, Walter R. (1985). The Effect of Age and Gender on Deviant Behavior: A Biopsychosocial Perspective. In *Gender and the Life-course*, ed. Alice S. Rossi. NY: Aldine.
- Greenberg, David F. (1977). Delinquency and the Age Structure of Society. *Contemporary Crisis* 1:189–223.
- Greenberg, David F. (1985). Age, Crime, and Social Explanation. *American Journal of Sociology*, 91(1): 1–21.
- Greenberg, David F. (2008). Age, sex, and racial distributions of crime. In E. Goode (Ed.), *Out of control: Assessing the general theory of crime* (pp. 38–48). Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Greenberg, David F., & Larkin, Nancy J. (1985). Age-Cohort Analysis of Arrest Rates. *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*, 1(3): 227-240.
- Hartwig, Frederick, & Dearing, Brian E. (1979). *Exploratory Data Analysis*. Beverly Hills, CA.: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Hirschi, Travis, & Gottfredson, Michael (1983). Age and the Explanation of Crime. *The American Journal of Sociology*, 89(3): 552-584.
- Hirschi, Travis, & Gottfredson, Michael (1985a). All Wise after the Fact Learning Theory, Again: Reply to Baldwin. *American Journal of Sociology*, 90(6): 1330-1333.
- Hirschi, Travis, & Gottfredson, Michael R. (1985b). Age and Crime, Logic and Scholarship: Comment on Greenberg. *The American Journal of Sociology*, 91(1): 22-27.

- Hirschi, Travis, & Gottfredson, Michael R. (1995). Control theory and the life-course perspective. *Studies on Crime and Crime Prevention*, 4(2): 131–142.
- Hirschi, Travis, & Hindelang, Michael J. (1977). Intelligence and delinquency: A revisionist review. *American Sociological Review*, 42, 571–587.
- Jennings, Wesley G., & Reingle, Jennifer M. (2012). On the number and shape of developmental/life-course violence, aggression, and delinquency trajectories: A state-of-the-art review. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 40: 472–489.
- Kanazawa, Satoshi (2003). Why productivity fades with age: The crime–genius connection. *Journal of Research in Personality* 37: 257–272.
- Kanazawa, Satoshi, & Still, Mary C. (2000). Why men commit crimes (and why they desist). *Sociological Theory*, 18(3): 434–447.
- Kuczumski Robert J., Ogden, Cynthia L., Guo, Shumei S., et al. (2000). CDC growth charts for the United States: Methods and development. National Center for Health Statistics. *Vital Health Stat* 11(246). 2002.
- Land, Kenneth C., McCall, Patricia L., & Cohen, Laurence E. (1989). Age structure and crime: Is there a connection? Paper presented at the Annual Meetings of the American Sociological Association, San Francisco.
- Laub, John H., & Sampson, Robert (2001). Understanding Desistance from Crime. In Michael Tonry (Ed.) *Crime and Justice: A Review of Research*, Vol. 28 (pp. 1-69). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Laub, John H., & Sampson, Robert J. (2003). *Shared Beginnings, Divergent Lives: Delinquent Boys to Age 70*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

- Lauritsen, Janet L. (1998). The Age-Crime Debate: Assessing the Limits of Longitudinal Self-Report Data. *Social Forces*, 77(1): 127-154.
- LeBlanc, Marc, & Loeber, Rolf (1998). Developmental Criminology Updated. In *Crime and Justice: A Review of Research*, Vol. 23 (pp. 115-198), edited by Michael Tonry. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lehman, Harvey C. (1953). *Age and Achievement*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Loeber, Rolf (2012). Does the study of the age-crime curve have a future? In R. Loeber & B. C. Welsh (Eds.), *The future of criminology* (pp. 11–19). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Loeber, Rolf, & Farrington, David P. (2012). The age-crime curve and its relevance for policy and interventions. In Bruinsma, G. J. N. and Weisburd, D. (Eds.) *Encyclopedia of Criminology and Criminal Justice*. New York: Springer-Verlag.
- Loeber, Rolf, & LeBlanc, Marc (1990). Toward a Developmental Criminology. In *Crime and Justice: A Review of Research*, Vol. 12, (pp. 375-473), edited by Michael Tonry and Norval Morris. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Lombroso, Cesare (1876/2006). *Criminal Man*, Translated and with a new introduction by Mary Gibson and Nicole Hahn Rafter. London: Duke University Press.
- Malina, Robert M., Bouchard, Claude, & Bar-Or, Oded (2004). *Growth, Maturation, and Physical Activity* (2nd Ed.). Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Maruna, Shadd (2001). *Making good: How ex-offenders reform and reclaim their lives*. Washington, D.C.: American Psychological Association.
- Matza, David (1964). *Delinquency and Drift*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

- Moffitt, Terrie E. (1993). Life-course-persistent and adolescence-limited antisocial behavior: A developmental taxonomy. *Psychological Review*, 100(4): 674-701.
- Montoye, Henry J. (1975). *Physical Activity and Health: An Epidemiologic Study of an Entire Community*, Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
- Nagin, Daniel S., & Land, Kenneth C. (1993). Age, criminal careers and population heterogeneity: Specification and estimation of a non-parametric, mixed poisson model. *Criminology*, 31(3): 327-362.
- Nagin, Daniel S., & Tremblay, Richard E. (1999). Trajectories of boys' physical aggression, opposition, and hyperactivity on the path to physically violent and nonviolent juvenile delinquency. *Child Development*, 70(5): 1181–1196.
- Nagin, Daniel S. & Tremblay, Richard E. (2005). What has been learned from group-based trajectory modeling?: Examples from physical aggression and other problem behaviors. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 602: 82-117.
- NIBRS (2012). National Incident Based Reporting System. Crimes by Age, Gender and Race. Downloaded on 12/1/2012 from <http://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/NACJD/series/128>
- Osgood, D. Wayne (2005). Making sense of crime and the life course. *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 602, 196–211.
- Osgood, D. Wayne (2012). Some future trajectories for life course criminology. In R. Loeber & B. C. Welsh (Eds.), *The future of criminology* (pp. 3–10). New York: Oxford University Press.

- Piquero, Alex R. (2008). Taking stock of developmental trajectories of criminal activity over the life course. In A. Liberman (Ed.), *The long view of crime: A synthesis of longitudinal research* (pp. 23–78). New York: Springer.
- Piquero, Alex R., Farrington, David P., & Blumstein, Alfred (2003). The criminal career paradigm. In M. Tonry (Ed.), *Crime and justice: A review of research* (Vol. 30, pp. 359–506). Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Piquero, Alex R., Farrington, David P., & Blumstein, Alfred (2007). *Key issues in criminal careers research: New analysis from the Cambridge study in delinquent development*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Pratt, Travis C., & Cullen, Francis T. (2000). The empirical status of Gottfredson and Hirschi's general theory of crime: A meta-analysis. *Criminology*, 38(3): 931-960.
- Quetelet, Adolphe. (1831). *Recherches sur le penchant au crime aux differens ages*. Brussels: M. Hayez.
- Quetelet, Adolphe. (1831/1984). *Research on the Propensity for Crime at Different Ages*. Translated and introduced by Sawyer F. Sylvester. Cincinnati: Anderson.
- Rafter, Nicole (2008). *The Criminal Brain: Understanding Biological Theories of Crime*. New York: New York University Press.
- Sampson, Robert J., & Laub, John H. (1993). *Crime in the Making: Pathways and Turning Points through Life*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Sampson, Robert J., & Laub, John H. (1997). Unraveling the Social Context of Physique and Delinquency: A New, Long-Term Look at the Gluecks' Classic Study. In Adrian Raine, Patricia Brennan, David Farrington, and Sarnoff Mednick (Eds.) *Biosocial Bases of Violence*, pp. 175-188. New York: Plenum Press.

- Shackell, L.F. (1925). The relation of dosage to effect. II. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 25(4): 275-288.
- Shavit, Yossi, & Rattner, Arye (1988). Age, crime, and the early life course. *American Journal of Sociology*, 93(6): 1457-1470.
- Shover, Neal (1996). *Great Pretenders: Pursuits and Careers of Persistent Thieves*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
- Shulman, Elizabeth P., Steinberg, Laurence D., & Piquero, Alex R. (2013). The Age-Crime Curve is Not Due to Differences in Economics. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 42:848–860.
- Skardhamar, Torbjørn (2009). Reconsidering the theory on adolescent-limited and life-course persistent anti-social behavior. *British Journal of Criminology*, 49, 863-878.
- Skardhamar, Torbjørn (2010). Distinguishing facts and artifacts in group-based modeling. *Criminology*, 48(1): 295-320.
- Sober, Elliott (1981). The Principle of Parsimony. *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science* 32(2): 145–156. doi:10.1093/bjps/32.2.145
- SPSS (2009). *SPSS Advanced Statistics 17.0*. Chicago: SPSS Statistics.
- Steffensmeier, Darrell, & Allan, Emilie Andersen (1995). Age-Inequality and Property Crime: The Effects of Age-Linked Stratification and Status-Attainment Processes on Patterns of Criminality Across the Life Course. In John Hagan and Ruth D. Peterson (Eds.), *Crime and Inequality*, (pp. 95-115), Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Steffensmeier, Darrell & Allan, Emilie Andersen (2000). Looking for Patterns: Gender, Age, and Crime. Pp. 83-113 in *Criminology*, edited by Joseph F. Sheley. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.

- Steffensmeier, Darrell J., Allan, Emilie Andersen, Harer, Miles D., & Streifel, Cathy (1989). Age and the distribution of crime. *The American Journal of Sociology*, 94(4): 803-831.
- Steffensmeier, Darrell J., & Streifel, Cathy (1991). Age, gender, and crime across three historical periods: 1935, 1960, and 1985. *Social Forces*, 69(3): 869-894.
- Steinberg, Laurence (2012). Should the Science of Adolescent Brain Development Inform Public Policy? *Issues in Science and Technology*, 28(3): 67-78.
- Steinberg, Laurence, & Monahan, Kathryn C. (2007). Age differences in resistance to peer influence. *Developmental Psychology*, 43, 1531–1543.
- Sterken, Elmer (2001). Endurance and Age: Evidence from Long-Distance Running Data. <http://som.eldoc.ub.rug.nl/FILES/reports/themeE/2001/01E47/01E47.pdf>
- Stolzenberg, Lisa, & D'Alessio, Stewart J. (2008). Co-Offending and the Age-Crime Curve. *Journal of Research in Crime and Delinquency*, 45(1): 65-86.
- Sweeten, Gary, Piquero, Alex R., & Steinberg, Laurence (2013). Age and the Explanation of Crime, Revisited. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, Feb, 2013.
- Telesca Donatello, Erosheva, Elena A., Kreager, Derek A., & Matsueda, Ross L. (2012). Modeling Criminal Careers as Departures from a Unimodal Age-Crime Curve. The Case of Marijuana Use. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 107(500): 1427-1440.
- Tittle, Charles R., & Grasmick, Harold G. (1997). Criminal Behavior and Age: A Test of Three Provocative Hypotheses. *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 88(1): 309–342.
- Tukey, John W. (1977). *Exploratory Data Analysis*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Turner, Michael G., & Piquero, Alex R. (2002). The stability of self-control. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 30: 457–471.

- Uggen, Christopher (2000). Work as a turning point in the life course of criminals: A duration model of age, employment, and recidivism. *American Sociological Review*, 67(4): 529–546.
- United Nations (2013). Eighth United Nations Survey of Crime Trends and Operations of Criminal Justice Systems, covering the period 2001 - 2002. Downloaded on February 13, 2013 from <http://www.unodc.org/pdf/crime/eighthsurvey/8pc.pdf>
- Van De Warker, Eli (1875). The relations of women to crime. *The Popular Science Monthly*, 8(1): 1-16.
- Vold, George B., Bernard, Thomas J., & Snipes, Jeffrey B. (2002). *Theoretical Criminology*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Walsh, Anthony (2009). Crazy by Design: A Biosocial Approach to the Age-Crime Curve. In Anthony Walsh, & Kevin M. Beaver (eds.). *Biosocial criminology: New directions in theory and research*. New York: Routledge.
- Walsh, Anthony, & Beaver, Kevin M. (2009). *Biosocial criminology: New directions in theory and research*. New York: Routledge.
- Wikström, Per-Olof H. (2009). Crime Propensity, Criminogenic Exposure and Crime Involvement in Early to Mid Adolescence. *Monatsschrift für Kriminologie und Strafrechtreform*, 92:253–266.
- Wilson, James Q. & Herrnstein, Richard (1985). *Crime and Human Nature*. New York: Simon and Schuster.
- Wolfgang, Marvin, Figlio, Robert, & Sellin, Thorsten (1972). *Delinquency in a Birth Cohort*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Wright, John Paul, Tibbetts, Stephen G., & Daigle, Leah E. (2008). *Criminals in the Making: Criminality across the life course*. Los Angeles: Sage.

Zhong, Hua (2005). *The age-crime relationship across time and offense types - A comparison of the United States and Taiwan*. Unpublished thesis. The Pennsylvania State University.